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List of Acronyms

Table 1. A list of acronyms used in this document.

Abbreviation	Meaning
ϵ_r	Bulk soil dielectric permittivity
AOI	Area of interest
AMD	Acid mine drainage
DEM	Digital elevation model
DHP	Digital Hemispherical photography
EGMS	European Ground Motion Service
EO	Earth Observation
FVC	Fractional Vegetation Cover
GM	Ground moisture
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HS	hyperspectral
HSI	Hyperspectral imaging
IEMS	Integrated Environment Monitoring System
<i>in situ</i>	in the natural or original position or place
IoT	Internet of things
IW mode	Interferometric Wide Swath mode
LAI	Leaf area index
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
ML	Machine Learning
MMU	Minimum mapping unit
MSI	Multispectral imaging
NASA	The National Aeronautics and Space Administration
PAI	Plant Area Index
PAIe	Effective Plant Area Index
PAN	Panchromatic
PS	Persistent scatterer
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
RPD	Ratio of Performance to Deviation
RVA	Real value area
SAM	Spectral angle mapper
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SED	Standard Error of prediction
SR	Species richness

Abbreviation	Meaning
STCD	SAR-time-series-change-detection
TSF	Tailings storage facility
UAV	Unmanned areal vehicle
VH	Cross-polarisation data
VV	Co-polarisation data
VWC	Volumetric water content
WCM	Water cloud model
XRD	X-ray diffraction
XRF	X-ray fluorecense

Executive Summary

Accuracy assessment is the final step in the development process which results in assessment for the quality of the application demonstrations done in the MultiMiner project. The Deliverable 4.2 “Report on evaluation of the novel products in terms of their accuracy and applicability in mineral exploration and mine site monitoring at the respective MultiMiner test sites” is a contribution of MultiMiner Task 4.2:” Thematic Accuracy Assessment Methods“. The Deliverable presents the evaluation of accuracy and applicability of novel Earth Observation (EO) and machine learning-based products developed within the MultiMiner project for mineral exploration and mine site monitoring across five European test sites.

Following an introduction in Chapter 1, Chapter 2 describes the thematic accuracy assessment procedures for MultiMiner application demonstrations, along with a summary of these methods. Chapter 3 contains a description of the result of end-user feedback and Chapter 4 ends with a conclusion.

Purpose and Scope

The goals of the report are to

- Report the actual results of the accuracy assessment of the MultiMiner application demonstrations and to summarize them.
- Summarize the feedback given by the miner site partners of the MultiMiner project.
- Provide an overall summary and assessment.

The document outlines:

- A comprehensive description of the various aspects of the accuracy assessment approaches and results across the MultiMiner test sites and applications: mineral exploration, vegetation monitoring, water quality and acid mine drainage, ground moisture monitoring, tailings storage facility (TSF) monitoring, dam and open pit stability monitoring and dust monitoring.
- A description of the end-user survey and the feedback received.
- A final assessment of all content.

Key Findings

- Each application required tailored approaches depending on whether the products represented thematic classifications or continuous variables, with a mix of quantitative metrics, regression models, and qualitative validation where necessary.
- EO and machine learning solutions successfully complement limited *in situ* data, enabling scalable monitoring across large and complex mining areas.
- Accuracy depends strongly on data quality, sampling design, and spatial/temporal alignment between EO and field measurements.
- Uncertainty is driven by factors such as mixed pixels, sensor limitations, spatial heterogeneity, and limited ground truth data, but can be mitigated through careful design and validation.
- Overall, the products are reliable for trend detection, spatial pattern analysis, and decision support, though precision varies by application and context.

End-User Feedback

The mine site partners of MultiMiner reported that the demonstrated applications:

- Provide valuable new insights and improved site-wide visibility
- Show high technical credibility and strong future potential
- Are relevant for monitoring, environmental management, reporting, and decision-making

However, operational deployment require:

- More validation and long-term testing.
- Better integration into workflows and user-friendly tools.
- Increased automation and data availability.

Overall Conclusion

Taken together, the technical accuracy assessments and the end-user feedback provide a consistent picture of the potential of the MultiMiner solutions. The validation activities demonstrated that the developed EO-based products can reliably support a wide range of mineral exploration and mine-site monitoring applications when applied with appropriate consideration of scale, reference data, sensor characteristics, and associated uncertainties. At the same time, the survey results confirm that end users recognize the added value of these approaches for operational monitoring, environmental management, reporting, compliance, and decision support.

1. Introduction

1.1 Project summary

The Multi-source and Multi-scale Earth observation and Novel Machine Learning Methods for Mineral Exploration and Mine Site Monitoring (MultiMiner) project developed novel data processing algorithms for cost-effective utilization of Earth Observation (EO) technologies for mineral exploration and mine site monitoring. The project was ongoing in 2023-2026. The objective of the MultiMiner project was to unlock the potential of EO data, airborne and low altitude as well as *in situ* data to support the entire mining life cycle. This was achieved by creating generic but highly innovative machine learning solutions. The project focused on new EO based exploration technologies for critical raw materials (CRM) to increase the probability of finding new sources within the EU, thereby strengthening the EU autonomy in the area of raw materials. MultiMiner's EO based exploration solutions have a low environmental impact, and are thus socially acceptable, economically efficient and improve safety. The project's solutions for mine site monitoring are foreseen to increase the transparency of mining operations as environmental impacts can be detected as early as possible and digital information of the currently unexploitable raw materials can be stored for future generations. The applicability of the developed algorithms was demonstrated in five European test sites. The Consortium of the MultiMiner project comprised 12 partners and 1 associated partner from research institutes, academia, consulting businesses and mining industry with interdisciplinary backgrounds in geology, remote sensing and machine learning. The members come from six EU member states which represent mining regions across Europe with diverse geology with evident potential for various types of CRM resources and thousands of operational and closed mines.

The strategic aim of MultiMiner was to provide Europe with novel scalable, robust and integrated mineral exploration and mine site monitoring solutions based primarily on multi-source EO data, facilitating discovery of critical raw materials (CRM) and their safe and environmentally sustainable exploitation in Europe. The project comprised the Consortium Partners listed in Table 2.

Table 2. The Consortium Partners of the MultiMiner project.

Name	Short name	Country
GEOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS	GTK	Finland
TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY	VTT	Finland
Nordkalk Oy Ab	Nordkalk	Finland
ELLINIKI ARCHI GEOLOGIKON KAI METALLEFTIKON EREVNON	HSGME	Greece
FONDATION EUROPEENNE DE LA SCIENCE	ESF	France

Name	Short name	Country
CESKA GEOLOGICKA SLUZBA	CGS	Czechia
MONTANUNIVERSITAET LEOBEN	MUL	Austria
BUNDESANSTALT FUER GEOWISSENSCHAFTEN UND ROHSTOFFE	BGR	Germany
GEOSPHERE AUSTRIA	Geosphere Austria	Austria
HELLAS GOLD S.A	HG	Greece
EFTAS FERNERKUNDUNG TECHNOLOGIETRANSFER GMBH	EFTAS	Germany
VEITSCH-RADEX GMBH & CO OG	RHI	Austria
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	TUM	Germany

CZECH
GEOLOGICAL
SURVEY

Federal Institute
for Geosciences and
Natural Resources

GeoSphere
Austria

RHI MAGNESITA

Technische Universität München

1.2 Purpose of Deliverable 4.2

The objective of this report is to describe the accuracy, reliability, and practical applicability of the innovative products developed as part of the MultiMiner project for mineral exploration and the monitoring of mining sites at the respective MultiMiner test sites. The report is intended to provide a comprehensive assessment framework that supports the validation of the developed methods and demonstrates their operational relevance for real-world mining environments.

The report documents and analyses the accuracy assessment results obtained from the MultiMiner application demonstrations conducted at the different test sites. This includes the evaluation of the performance of the developed products and workflows in terms of their robustness, consistency, and suitability for supporting mineral exploration activities and environmental monitoring tasks at mine sites.

In addition, the deliverable summarizes and discusses feedback from the mining partners involved in the MultiMiner project. Their practical experiences and assessments contribute to the evaluation of the operational usability, added value, and potential limitations of the developed products, thereby helping to identify opportunities for future improvements and recommendations for their continued deployment and use.

2. Thematic accuracy assessment procedures for MultiMiner application demonstrations

2.1 Overview

All groups involved in the development of the MultiMiner applications have already outlined their plans for the accuracy assessment of their respective applications in deliverable D4.1 Part 2. This document is based on and builds upon those descriptions. For this document, a Section E has now been added to each of Sections 2.2 to 2.8, detailing how the assessment was actually carried out. Some groups have also revised the texts previously written in Sections A–D, replacing the planned work with the work actually carried out. The teams were given guidance on which content to include in the accuracy assessment. The content included in sections 2.2 to 2.8 was provided by the respective development teams and has been revised solely for the purposes of consistency and clarity. Each section is structured as follows: after a short introduction and information about the background and commonly used accuracy assessment methods for the application each chapter is divided into A–E.

A describes the product regarding accuracy assessment with *A1 Product description* and *A2* an overview of the *accuracy requirements*. Part *B* for each application is divided into the description of EO data (*B1*) and *in situ* data (*B2*) input. Some application inputs concerning *in situ* data can be found in *D 4.1 Part 1 The Fieldguide Book*. Given the characteristics of the previous parts a recommendation concerning sampling design is performed in *C Sampling design evaluation*. Part *D* contains a recommendation about accuracy measurement. In part *E*, the accuracy assessment actually performed is reported.

The task Integrated 3D mine site monitoring is the combination of the task dam stability and open pit stability monitoring.

Task information concerning test sites and contributors can be found in Table 3.

Table 3. Task information on test site and thematic task leaders in MultiMiner project demonstrations.

Task	Test sites	Thematic task leader
Mineral exploration	Hochfilzen, Chalkidiki, Kallynthiri	BGR
Vegetation monitoring	Hochfilzen	VTT
Water quality and AMD	Chalkidiki, Kirki	CGS
Ground moisture monitoring	Ihalainen	VTT
Integrated TSF monitoring	Chalkidiki	BGR
Integrated 3D mine site monitoring	Ihalainen	GTK
Dust monitoring	Chalkidiki, Ihalainen	CGS

2.2 Accuracy assessment approach for the demonstrating MultiMiner application mineral exploration

Hyperspectral remote sensing data has been used for mineral exploration since the 1980s. This is when the Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) by NASA was first mounted on an aircraft and field spectrometers were advanced enough to provide high quality ground truth data (Goetz, 2009). In the 2000s, the Earth Observing-1 satellite, carrying the Hyperion hyperspectral imager, was successfully launched by NASA. In the last ten years, high spectral resolution hyperspectral satellite imagers PRISMA, EnMAP and EMIT have been increasingly used in academic mineral exploration studies.

In this section, an overview will be given on the accuracy assessment work carried out in Work Package 2 (Scalable Mineral Prospectivity Tools) and Work Package 4 (Site Demonstrations). In practice, the work was done in the context of Task 4.3 (Demonstration of Mineral Prospectivity Mapping).

A Product description regarding accuracy assessment

A1 Product description

In the course of the MultiMiner project, different types of mineral maps were produced. These maps are listed (Table 4). The mineral map products are described in Table 5.

Table 4. Product description mineral exploration – thematic maps.

Demonstration of mineral exploration – product description - thematic maps				
	Description	<i>in situ</i> data	UAV/EO	Classes/segments
Spectral feature map	Spectral features of interest highlight different mineral assemblages and alteration zones in the study areas	Point spectral measurements collected in the field, hand specimens collected for later laboratory analysis	<p>Chalkidiki: Enmap satellite data, hyperspectral UAV data, photogrammetry</p> <p>Hochfilzen: Enmap satellite data, hyperspectral airborne data, hyperspectral UAV data, photogrammetry</p> <p>Kallyntiri: hyperspectral UAV data, photogrammetry</p>	classification

Vegetation map	Vegetation mask	-	Hyperspectral UAV data	classification
Spectral library	Classification tasks (data analysis)	This is <i>in situ</i> data		classification

Table 5. Product description mineral exploration – enhanced mineral maps for exploration.

Demonstration of mineral exploration – enhanced mineral maps for exploration	
Map	Description
Mineral proxy maps / Distal-proximal footprint marker maps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chalkidiki clay and mica maps • Hochfilzen carbonate mineral maps • Kallyntiri carbonate, clay and mica maps

A2 Accuracy requirements

It is not possible to give general accuracy requirements for the mineral exploration application, because the requirements vary on a case-by-case basis. Commercial applications may have lower accuracy requirements than scientific applications. In all cases, where accuracy is being measured, what is being measured is how close the remotely sensed result is to what can be observed in the field. Some key points to consider, in this context, are the following:

- Ensure that some ground truth data is available from the key lithologies of interest
- Consider leaving out some heavily vegetated areas (e.g. few rock outcrops, rock outcrops covered by lichens or other vegetation)
- Acquire field spectral measurements from horizontal, not vertical surfaces, so that they can be compared against remote sensing data.

B Accuracy assessment inputs

B1 EO and drone data input

The key remote sensing data sources of the mineral exploration application are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Input EO and drone data for mineral mapping.

	Sensor	Resolution		
	Optical	Spatial	Spectral	Temporal
EnMAP	HSI	30 m	420 – 2450 nm	27 days
Hyperspectral UAV	HSI	6-8 cm	400 – 2500 nm	N/A
Photogrammetric UAV	RGB	2 cm	400-700 nm	N/A

B2 *In situ* data input

To ensure that accuracy assessments could be carried out with a sufficient amount of *in situ* data, several field campaigns were completed during the project. The goal of these campaigns was twofold: i) collect data and samples from the study areas ii) pinpoint the areas of interest (focus areas for remote sensing data analysis). A total of four campaigns were conducted, two of them in Hochfilzen and one in Chalkidiki and Kallyntiri each. In these areas, point spectral field data was obtained from profiles and representative lithologies. Furthermore, field data was acquired of calibration targets and homogenous areas (e.g. paved roads, parking lots) so that this information could be used to atmospherically correct the remote sensing UAV and manned airborne data. All metadata was carefully recorded in field sheets and the metadata was furthermore later ingested into the MultiMiner project database.

C Sampling design evaluation

The sampling design used in the mineral exploration application was *stratified sampling*. In practice, the geology of the study areas was carefully studied before the field campaigns, and during the campaign, the aim was to get a good representation of the key lithologies of the study areas. Of each such lithology, a random sample was then collected. When possible, rock surfaces with a minimal amount of vegetation were chosen for spectral measurements that were carried out simultaneously with sample collection. Each spectral measurement was accompanied by sample collecting and the collected samples were later taken for X-Ray Diffraction (XRD; Chalkidiki, Hochfilzen, Kallyntiri) and X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF; Kallyntiri) laboratory analysis to get the mineralogy and geochemistry of the samples. The goal of this protocol was to ensure that field data could be used to support atmospheric corrections, in addition to accuracy assessments. Moreover, in the Chalkidiki and Hochfilzen study areas, transects/profiles were done to collect field spectral measurements and samples from the key lithologies. Practices outlined in the MultiMiner field guidebook (Paulick et al., 2024) were followed during the field campaigns.

It should be noted that apart from the field spectral measurements and the accompanying rock sample collection, a separate soil sample set was collected from the Chalkidiki study area. These samples, collected using a systematic sample design (a regular grid) were later analyzed using the Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) technique. The aim of this work was to get an enhanced understanding on the prospectivity of different areas of the site.

D Accuracy measurement recommendation

As key observation made during the project: the mineral exploration team of Task 4.3 (Demonstration of Mineral Prospectivity Mapping) recommends conducting two field surveys: one for preparation and planning and another for collecting an extensive field spectral dataset and samples. The second field campaign can be used to optimize the sampling that is already started on the first field campaign. When there is sufficient time between the two field campaigns, the team carrying out the work can do laboratory analysis on the samples and form an understanding of the geology of the study area. This approach ensures that the field sample set is representative.

E Accuracy assessment actually performed

The inputs and requirements of the accuracy assessment protocols are given in sections A-D (above).

In T4.3 (Demonstration of Mineral Prospectivity Mapping) of MultiMiner, due to the nature of the work that was conducted, absolute accuracy assessments were not carried out using measures like F1 Score or Cohen's Kappa -metric. On the contrary, relative assessments were made by comparing the

wavelength positions of the field data to those of the remotely sensed UAV, manned airborne and satellite data.

Implementation Status

The accuracy assessment carried out in Task 4.3 (Demonstration of Mineral Prospectivity Mapping) protocols are described in sections A-E (above).

Additional information

The results are planned to be published in one or several scientific articles and any data that accompanies those publications will be released in the MultiMiner Zenodo ([Zenodo](#)). The metadata of the field measurements will be stored in the MultiMiner Database described in D4.1 Field Guidebook ([Deliverable No 4.1. Part 1: Field Guidebook](#)).

Summary of Accuracy Assessments

In Work Package 2 (Scalable Mineral Prospectivity Tools), hyperspectral remote sensing data was acquired across multiple scales — UAV, manned airborne, and satellite — to produce mineral maps and evaluate their accuracy for mineral exploration. Field campaigns across three study areas provided essential ground truth through spectral measurements and laboratory analyzed rock samples. A stratified sampling strategy ensured representative coverage of key lithologies, with additional systematic sampling in Chalkidiki for geochemical analysis.

Because accuracy needs vary by application, no universal accuracy threshold was defined. Instead, the project emphasized best practices: conducting two field campaigns, ensuring sufficient ground truth, and focusing on minimally vegetated rock surfaces. Rather than using absolute accuracy metrics, the team performed relative assessments by comparing spectral wavelength positions between field and remotely sensed data. Results and accompanying datasets will be published and archived through Zenodo and the MultiMiner database.

2.3 Accuracy assessment approach for the demonstrating MultiMiner application vegetation monitoring

Vegetation monitoring in mine sites can provide information about the status and ecological development of the site. Vegetation monitoring in the context of mine sites is often performed in simple, if not simplistic ways. In a recent review of RS methods to assess mine site rehabilitation for ecological outcomes, most approaches (85%) rely on either supervised methods or visual interpretation (McKenna et al., 2020), with mainly multispectral imagery (45% of studies used a simple Normalized Difference Vegetation Index). Hyperspectral imagery or image time series analysis were used only in 6 and 1 studies, respectively, in the context of mine site revegetation studies. In the field of ML-based time series analysis for environmental monitoring, many approaches are still supervised and rely on a single or dual data sources (Molinier and Kilpi, 2019).

Satellite RS offers an array of sensors and methods for comprehensive, spatially explicit mapping and monitoring of vegetation vitality, biomass, and related environmental and human-induced processes. Its continuous recording of spectral vegetation indices, serving as proxies for biomass and vitality, along with the calculation of biophysical variables such as Leaf Area Index (LAI), Fractional Vegetation Cover (FVC) and Species Richness (SR), enables the detection of trends, disturbances, and management practices. This supports environmental monitoring, reporting and decision making. The application of the methods and taken approaches for accuracy assessment vary widely and largely depend on the specific use case at hand.

A Product description regarding accuracy assessment

A1 Product description

For application demonstration for vegetation monitoring in the MultiMiner project five maps are produced (Table 7). Two maps based on the Leaf Area Index (LAI) and the Fractional Vegetation Cover (FVC) and three based on the parameters of Species Richness (SR), Shannon and Simpson diversity.

Table 7. Product description vegetation monitoring.

Demonstration of vegetation monitoring			
MAP	Leaf Area Index (LAI) map	Fractional Vegetation Cover (FVC) map	Species Richness (SR) map, Shannon Diversity map, Simpson Diversity map
<i>In situ data</i>	LAI	FVC	SR and dominant species (2023); SR and species abundance (2024)
EO data	Sentinel- 2 PlanetScope UAV (MSI and/or HSI)	Sentinel- 2 PlanetScope UAV (MSI and/or HSI)	Sentinel-2 time series PlanetScope time series EnMAP UAV (HSI)
classes/segments	Continuous variable	Continuous variable	Continuous variables

A2 Accuracy requirements

The following description is a recommendation for vegetation monitoring regarding requirements for accuracy assessment. The vitality status of the flora is observed at certain times throughout the year (recommendation 4 times a year i. e. month 03/06/09/12) or permanently when image material is provided by optical sensors and compared with a certain status of the last status. Some regions cannot be visited for *in situ* sampling in the winter due to snow cover. Recommended imagery such as Sentinel-2 require good weather conditions (cloud-free, good lighting). Depending on the cloud cover and the radiometric quality of the satellite images, there are usually 15 to 25 suitable recording dates available, which are distributed more or less evenly over the vegetation period.

The MMU detected area should be about 20x20 m such that a sufficient number of full pixels are available for evaluation.

LAI and FVC are essential for evaluating soil erosion potential and nutrient runoff, as areas with robust dense vegetation typically reduces soil erosion and have a greater capacity to intercept and absorb nutrients before they enter aquatic systems. Regular monitoring of FVC and LAI changes with Sentinel-2 allows for the identification of vulnerable areas prone to erosion or nutrient leaching. High-resolution hyperspectral imagery is known to provide stratification at a very fine scale (Schmidtlein and Sassini, 2004).

Obtaining *in situ* LAI data generally involves a structured approach that is applicable across the various ecosystems of interest. Measurements are carried out often over several years to capture seasonal and developmental variations in vegetation. A key technique in this process is Digital Hemispherical photography (DHP), which involves capturing images of the canopy from both below and above. This method is crucial for estimating the gap fraction, a measure of the sky visible through the canopy, which is indicative of the leaf area. In each selected site, multiple plots are systematically photographed over regular intervals to gather comprehensive data. These photographs are then processed to estimate the gap fraction from which the Plant Area Index (PAI) and effective Plant Area Index (PAI_e) are calculated. Adjustments are made in the data to account for the inability of upward facing images to distinguish between foliage and woody material. This involves applying established ratios for different forest types to accurately differentiate these components. The final step involves calculating the LAI and LAI_e from PAI and PAI_e values, incorporating corrections for woody material (Brown et al 2025).

Species richness in vegetation monitoring is a widely used parameter and can provide a good basis for further monitoring and is an essential part of characterizing biodiversity (Gould, 2000). Species evenness could be taken into account as species richness is recorded (Zhao et al., 2021). Species richness could be defined by the number of plant species and the identification of 1–3 dominant species to keep the field work costs and the effort within reasonable limits and ensure good comparability. Acquiring visual species coverage estimates allows further insights on the species distribution and evenness with little added fieldwork time. The resulting new parameters of Shannon and Simpson diversity describe heterogeneity and the dominance of few species, respectively (Fauvel et al., 2020). It should be noted that species diversity has sensitivity regarding environmental variables like temperature or topography (Vila-Viçosa et al., 2020).

For a representative statement about revegetation, the species quantification or identification in addition to the indices is recommended. A close look at pioneer plants would also be a good approach considering revegetation. Depending on the species it would be important to execute the field

campaign during the vegetation growing season. Especially due to the indices a suggestion is to sample the *in situ* data within a sampling quadrat.

B Accuracy assessment inputs

B1 EO data input

In the MultiMiner project, Sentinel-2 data will be used to produce a vegetation map with a temporal resolution once per summer for LAI and FVC and a dense time series with all available data for the input to model SR. The performance of Sentinel-2 will be compared to similarly implemented PlanetScope data. UAV HSI drone imagery was acquired in the July-August 2024 (Table 8).

Table 8. Input EO data for vegetation monitoring.

Vegetation monitoring – Input EO data					
	Sensor	Resolution			MMU
	optical	spatial	spectral	temporal	Detected area
Sentinel-2	MSI	10 – 20 m	400 – 2200 nm	1 per summer for LAI and FVC dense time series, all available data from 2020 to 2024 for SR	10 x 10 m
PlanetScope	MSI	3 m	430 – 890 nm	all available cloudfree data from 2020 to 2024 for SR	3 x 3 m
EnMAP	HSI	30 m	420 - 2450 nm	1 image (August 2024)	30 x 30 m
Multispectral drone	MSI	5 cm	450 – 850 nm	once a year or less	
Hyperspectral drone	HSI	6-20 cm	400 – 2500 nm	once a year or less	1 x 1 m

B2 *In situ* data input

In situ data for vegetation monitoring were measured in 1x1 m² units. For each sample all sample variables are recorded (Table 9). Species Richness (SR) required counting the number of plant species per quadrat. Additional abundance and dominance estimates supported interpreting its variation and strength of relationship with remote sensing data: In 2023, 1-3 most dominant species were defined. In 2024, dominance was replaced with absolute species coverage (%) estimates of all present species which allowed deriving additional plant diversity indicators Shannon Diversity Index and Simpson's Diversity Index. The LAI is measured with a LAI2000 device and the FVC is calculated from *in situ* digital photographs. A detailed description of *in situ* data acquired in 2023 is described in *D4.1 Part 1 MultiMiner Field Guidebook*.

Table 9. Input *in situ* data for vegetation monitoring.

Vegetation monitoring- Input <i>in situ</i> data		
Variable	<i>In situ</i> measurements at each quadrat	Number of samples

Species Richness (2023 & 2024) Shannon Diversity, 2024 Simpson Diversity, 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of plant species • dominant species (1–3 main plant species) in 2023 • absolute species coverage (%) in 2024 	32 in August 2023 77 in July 2024
LAI	with a LAI2000 device, either at quadrat centre, or averaged when needed	32 in 2024 (averaged) 77 in 2024
FVC	digital photograph (FVC calculated offline from the photograph)	32 in 2024 80 in 2024

C Sampling design evaluation

Regarding the product type of vegetation monitoring and the characteristics of input EO data and *in situ* reference data, the following practices for sampling design are suggested.

Vegetation monitoring always goes hand in hand with *in situ* sampling. An optimal sampling design can be recognized as having low cost but without losing necessary spatial information. In addition, a high precision is desired for estimation and mapping vegetation cover. For the aimed RS derived product it can be useful to define criteria of environmental gradients for a stratification, concerning the task. For a stratification, an initial classification should be generated, regarding revegetation topic and targeted *in situ* data input. Thus, the stratification makes sampling more efficient. A buffer on the initial classification is recommended to avoid edge effects. Since the topic is revegetation, control classes next to the mine site are useful.

A two phase sampling with stratified random approach could be the best way to approach the question of accuracy in the context of vegetation monitoring. It is also becoming widespread in vegetation studies due to its simple but robust-application and satisfactory accuracy results (Olofsson et al., 2014; Michalcová et al., 2011; Roleček et al., 2007).

To establish a connection between EO data and *in situ* data and especially the calculation of indices, the grid (10x10 m) creation for later sample selection should be aligned with Sentinel-2 pixels. To reduce autocorrelation, the distance between the sample locations should be taken into account. Since the mining areas are comparatively small in size but a sufficient number of samples are needed, the distance between the plots cannot be increased too much. The number of sampling locations can be limited due to the constraints in access to the mining area and resources. Thus, the technique of simple random sampling could lead to undersampling of the classes (van Oort, 2007). The proportional allocation to the strata weights has a positive effect on parameters such as overall and producer accuracy (Olofsson, 2021). The recommendation regarding the allocation of sample size to strata is to increase the sample size for rare vegetation classes to achieve a sufficient standard error and to allocate the remaining samples roughly proportional to the area occupied by the common classes (Olofsson et al., 2014).

Due to standard vegetation monitoring protocols a sampling quadrat of 1x1 m is recommended to enable a comparison to other studies (Baxter, 2014). The use of cluster sampling is only recommended if it provides cost savings or if a cluster unit is needed regarding the objective (Olofsson et al., 2014). During stratification it could be useful to check the representativity of vegetation distribution of the 1 m² in comparison to the 100 m² resolution to Sentinel-2. The plot size can be crucial when it comes to physical vegetation structure.

The sampling design method applied for vegetation monitoring is described in detail in D4.1 MultiMiner field guidebook Chapter 3.1.7 *In situ vegetation measurements*.

D Accuracy measurement recommendation

In order to validate the three types of vegetation maps, an accuracy assessment against the *in situ* measurements is recommended. Continuous map values resulting from the regression methods is the common output in vegetation related studies. The so-called statistical goodness-of-fit measures are often recommended to be used. Above all, to get the best product performance, comprehensive accuracy assessments should be done. RMSE has been used most often in literature (Richter et al., 2011).

Furthermore, the continuous values of each map could be stratified and then accuracy measurements using the confusion matrix table and related metrics could be performed.

E Accuracy assessment actually performed

Implementation Status

Most parts of the accuracy assessment design were implemented as planned. The *in situ* measurements were conducted on 22.8-24.8 in 2023 and on 20.7-30.7 in 2024. A summary of the measured parameters and the number of samples is shown in Table 9.

As suggested in section C, the samples were distributed according to stratified random sampling strategy where the number of samples per similarly rehabilitated stratification polygon was roughly proportional to its area. The sample size of the less common control areas was increased by couple quadrats.

The concerns related to spatial autocorrelation were addressed by applying a minimum distance of 60m between most sampling locations. Furthermore, Moran's I test with 5-12 nearest neighbours was added to confirm the independence of the samples. Out of the 77 vegetation samples, 52 samples were confirmed to be spatially independent. The other 25 samples corresponded to 5 clusters of neighbouring pixels (a centre pixel and 4 adjacent pixels). The main purpose of adding the quadrat clusters was to assess spatial heterogeneity and representativeness of the quadrats for each stratification area.

Due to the time constraints and the high number of species present, vegetation distribution was not analysed for the whole 100m² resolution Sentinel-2 pixel in comparison to the 1m² quadrats. Instead, the quadrat was assumed to represent the whole pixel.

EO Data Used

All collected EO data sources described in Table 8 were used to predict at least one of the target variables: the single date HSI imagery (drone and EnMAP), Sentinel-2 time series and PlanetScope time series were used in the plant diversity predictions, and the closest dates of each listed MSI data source were used in FVC and LAI estimation. HSI drone imagery acquired in July-August 2024 covered only a part of reference quadrats (51 out of the 77 quadrats).

Processing and Integration of *In Situ* Measurements with EO Data

FVC was computed from digital nadir photographs using RGB band ratios and thresholds aimed at separating green pixels from the rest (section B2). Only the pixels falling within the masked area inside the quadrat frame were analysed. LAI was measured with LICOR LAI 2200-C device. Manual bias

corrections based on FVC estimates and *in situ* photographs, as well as sensor corrections in LAI software, were performed afterwards to account for short vegetation outside the field-of-view and incorrect in field measures due to challenging or varying illumination conditions. Both FVC and LAI data were used in training and validating regression models.

Species Richness (SR) corresponded directly with the number of species detected. In 2024, the abundance data expressed with Braun-Blanquet scale was first quantified according to (Tüxen&Ellenberg, 1937) scale and then inserted into Shannon Diversity and Simpson's diversity equations alongside SR. The 3 output plant diversity indicators per quadrat were stored into csv-tables together with the corresponding point coordinates and used as training and validation data for 3 Random Forest Regression models.

Statistical Measures Applied

As planned, several statistical measures, including RMSE, R^2 and MAE, were computed against the *in situ* measurements. Additionally, Pearson's r and Spearman's rank correlations have been computed to assess both the multicollinearity between features and their expected predictive performance in relation to the target variables. To date, the outputted maps have not been further stratified for accuracy measurements.

Additional information

Accuracy Metrics, Validation Methods, and Uncertainty Assessment

Despite the minimum distance between most sampling locations, Moran's I test was considered necessary to evaluate whether the clustered samples could be considered independent and unbiased for the model training. Due to the increased spatial autocorrelation between the 25 clustered samples, the clusters were excluded from model training. They were considered only as an additional held-out test set for the performance of the final model. The remaining 52 spatially independent samples formed the training and validation data set for nested 5-fold cross-validation.

To avoid data leakage, hyperparameter tuning and Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) were performed during the inner cross-validation loop of the nested 5-fold cross-validation. Already before RFE, simple prefiltering of features was performed to exclude near constant and highly correlated features.

During cross-validation, the mean and standard deviation of R^2 value were resolved from the 5 folds, and the predictions were stored for a pooled accuracy assessment. The pooled predictions were eventually plotted against the reference data as a combined regression plot to allow visual assessment of model generalizability. RMSE, R^2 and MAE were also computed for the pooled data. Once the hyperparameter tuning was completed, final model was trained with all training data and the same accuracy metrics were recomputed for the held-out test data comprised of the 25 clustered points.

Representativeness of the Reference Data

Representativeness of *in situ* data was visually assessed based on the photographs taken of the sampling areas and their surroundings. Additionally, the distribution of reference data was visualized as a map and as a histogram to become aware of any potential outliers or edge cases in the data.

Criteria and Tolerances for Spatial and Temporal Alignment Between EO and Field Data

To ensure sufficient spatial alignment between EO and field data, the field measurements were collected at the center coordinates of the 10m resolution Sentinel-2 pixel. For PlanetScope data, the pixel closest to the quadrat center coordinates was used which should ensure that at least majority of the quadrat aligned with the pixel. Visual assessment of the alignment was performed using QGIS. In the case of UAV imagery, all pixels within 1x1m window from the quadrat centre were extracted.

In addition to visual checks, uncertainties related to the EO data were addressed by quality masks, removing pixels outside the AOI and enforcing thresholds for the acceptable range of values typical for vegetation. Smoothing algorithms, such as LOESS, and moving window outlier detection using cutoff deviation were also applied for pixel time series.

Practical Challenges Encountered During Data Collection and Analysis

Regarding the practical challenges, two planned sampling locations had to be shifted on site due to their closeness to steep slopes or changed boundary of the open pit. Also, the HSI drone flight plan had to be adjusted on site because of the slopes and the varying lighting conditions. As a result, 51 quadrats out of 77 were covered by the flights and corresponded well to the hand-held reference spectra.

Summary of Accuracy Assessment

Key Outcomes of the Comparison Between EO Products and Reference Data

EO data can be used to expand the spatial coverage of *in situ* data to find sub-areas with similar vegetation behaviour. However, extrapolating the models on non-vegetated pixels or forest not represented in the training data may yield unexpected results.

Main Uncertainties and Identified Limitations

Due to the mismatch in size between the sampled quadrats and the remotely sensed pixels, mixed pixels and edge pixels between different vegetation types have an increased risk of over- or underestimating plant diversity compared to homogenous pixels.

Overall Reliability of the Produced Maps for Monitoring and Decision-Making in the MultiMiner Project

The produced maps should be considered as a scale from low to high diversity rather than precise species counts, since Random Forest regression tends to avoid predicting the most extreme values. Due to the imbalance of high versus low diversity samples in the training data, this challenge is visible especially in the cross-validation predictions where the value range of training data is more restricted for some folds.

2.4 Accuracy assessment approach for the demonstrating MultiMiner application water quality and acid mine drainage

Accuracy assessment methods for water quality and acid mine drainage (AMD) monitoring using EO data commonly include the following aspects:

- Validation with *in situ* measurements: *In situ* water quality measurements can be used to validate remotely sensed data, ensuring that EO methods accurately capture characteristics of water quality and AMD.
- Image classification: Satellite imagery can be used to predict or classify various water quality parameters or identify AMD.
- Change detection analysis: By comparing multiple satellite images over time, changes in water quality or AMD can be detected and quantified. Accuracy assessment methods involve evaluating the consistency of detected changes with field observations.

A Product description regarding accuracy assessment

A1 Product description

A common product for water quality and AMD monitoring using EO data is the detection of harmful substances such as heavy metals in water bodies. Earth Observation data can be used to identify and track pollutants that are released from mining activities into nearby water courses. By analysing satellite images and other RS data, researchers can detect changes in water colour, turbidity, and other indicators of pollution.

Moreover, AMD release from mine waste rock, tailings and mine structures, such as pits and underground workings, is primarily a function of the mineralogy of local rock material, i.e. mainly secondary minerals associated with sulfide bearing material, and the availability of water and oxygen. The typical AMD pattern leads to accumulation of Fe sulfates, oxy-hydroxides and oxides in a spatial and temporal sequence that represents the buffering of an acidic solution as it moves away from its source (Kopačková and Hladiková, 2014; Montero et al., 2005; Swayze et al., 2000). By analysing satellite imagery and spectral signatures, researchers can also track the presence of iron oxides in water bodies and assess the extent of the AMD pollution (Kopačková and Hladiková, 2014; Glaesser et al, 2011).

In the MultiMiner project, different raster maps will be created (Table 10). The first map is based on water samples and MSI data taken with droneborne Parrot Sequoia (Figure 1). Two other maps will be created with the information from mining company collected data in Environment Monitoring System IEMS and different EO data, resulting in varying spatial and temporal spatial resolutions of the output maps.

Table 10. Product description water quality and AMD.

Demonstration of water quality and AMD – product description						
Map type	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	<i>In situ</i> data	EO data	Sample unit/distribution	Classes/segments
raster map	2–3 cm	one data acquisition	water samples acquired simultaneously with drone-based data acquisition (see B2)	Parrot Seq	1 to 1 (1 sample per one dataset)	continuous variable, classification
raster map	3 m	weekly	Environment Monitoring System IEMS platform	Planet Scope	stratified random sampling	continuous variable, classification
raster map	10–20 m	monthly	Environment Monitoring System IEMS platform	Sentinel-2	stratified random sampling	classification

Figure 1. Measuring water quality: collecting water samples together with acquiring the spectral water data (multispectral Parrot Sequoia imaging and Ocean Optics data) at Chalkidiki area.

A2 Accuracy requirements

When monitoring water quality and AMD using EO data, accuracy requirements are crucial to ensure reliable and meaningful results.

The satellite imagery should have a high enough spatial resolution, i.e. sub-metre to few metres precision, to distinguish small-scale water bodies and potential sources of pollution, such as mine tailings and runoff points. EO data should cover a wide range of spectral bands (i.e. at least visible to near-infrared, ideally spanning up to short wave infrared spectral range) to accurately detect and differentiate between various water quality parameters, such as turbidity, chlorophyll levels, and dissolved minerals. Accurate georeferencing of EO data is essential for identifying specific water bodies and monitoring changes in their quality over time. Furthermore, regular and frequent monitoring is essential to capture dynamic changes in water quality over time, especially in response to mining activities or environmental incidents. For radiometric accuracy, a precise radiometric calibration ensures accurate quantification of reflectance values, which is crucial for deriving water quality indicators from satellite data. In addition, field validation and ground truthing are necessary to verify the accuracy of satellite-derived water quality parameters and ensure reliable and consistent monitoring results.

B Accuracy assessment inputs

B1 EO data input

In Table 11 the EO data input is shown regarding sensor, resolution, MMU and the preprocessing level used for the product generation in water quality and AMD monitoring.

Table 11. Input EO data for water quality and AMD.

Water quality and AMD – Input EO data						
	Sensor	Resolution			MMU	Pre-processing level
	optical	spatial	spectral range	temporal	Detected area	
Parrot Sequoia	MultispectralVNIR	2–3 cm	530–810 nm (4 bands)	one date	patches covering the sampled sites	image reflectance
Planet scope	Multispectral VNIR	3 m	455–860 nm (4 or 8 bands)	multitemporal	whole defined AOI	image reflectance
Sentinel-2	Multispectral VNIR/SWIR	10–20 m	448–909 nm (13 bands)	multitemporal	whole defined AOI	image reflectance

B2 In situ data input

Water samples are taken from shallow water creeks or by droneborne open water sampler. The differences between the two mining sites and the measurement parameters are summarised in Table 12 and illustrated in Figure 2. As monitoring data from IEMS is also used for Chalkidiki mine site it is listed here in Table 12. The number of water samples in Chalkidiki is estimated to be 17, complemented by 33 monitoring points from IEMS. At Kirki, 30 water samples are planned to be taken.

Table 12. Input in situ data for water quality and AMD.

Water quality and AMD – Input <i>in situ</i> data		
Water sampling from shallow creeks	Chalkidiki	pH, dissolved Fe, solid particles, heavy metals, Secchi depth
	Kirki	pH, dissolved Fe, solid particles, heavy metals, TOC and turbidity
Open water sampling by drone-borne open water sampler	Kirki	pH, redox, conductivity, temperature, dissolved oxygen
Monitoring data (IEMS)	Chalkidiki	pH, diss Fe, heavy metals, colour

Figure 2. Sampling points for water quality and AMD– IEMS the monitoring system: 3-year average pH (year 2021–2023) and planned MultiMiner water sampling points shown as blue crosses.

C Sampling design evaluation

Optimal sampling design for water quality and AMD monitoring using EO data involves selecting sampling locations strategically to represent the variability of water quality and substrate parameters across the study area. Considering the product details and the *in situ* and EO data, the following sampling design plan is made.

The idea is to apply random sampling to provide a representative accuracy assessment. A stratification, based on location/proximity to mining sites or land use is suggested for the study area. An incorporated analysis of water flow patterns to capture the variability of water quality parameters (Haas et al., 2009) shall be the following step. The random distribution within each stratum could be performed using high-resolution Google Earth images, also taking into consideration the accessibility of the sites, i.e. safety and ability to walk while carrying the equipment.

GIS and image analysis techniques should be utilized to identify areas with potentially different pollutant concentrations or potential sources of contamination. The approach taken in MultiMiner combines pre-classification based on location/proximity to mining sites or land use with the analysis of water flow patterns to capture the variability of water quality parameters. This approach helps to streamline the sampling process and ensures that key areas of concern are adequately monitored and that they fit into random stratified sampling category.

D Accuracy measurement recommendation

With information from product description, accuracy assessment inputs and sampling design, a good practice for accuracy measurements is described here. Classification accuracy can be assessed through ground truth validation or comparison with known data sources. Overall, combining EO data with ground truth validation while employing performance metrics (e.g., kappa coefficient and regression metrics), can provide a comprehensive assessment of the accuracy of water quality and AMD monitoring methods.

E Accuracy assessment actually performed

Implementation Status

- The planned accuracy assessment was implemented following the concepts outlined in Sections A–D.
- EO data from Parrot Sequoia (2–3 cm, VNIR, one date), PlanetScope (3 m, VNIR, multitemporal), and Sentinel-2 (10–20 m, VNIR/SWIR, multitemporal) were used. All datasets were processed to image reflectance level.
- *In situ* water quality measurements and samples were collected at Chalkidiki (26 samples + 33 IEMS monitoring points) and Kirki (18 samples, including drone-borne open water sampling). Parameters measured included pH, dissolved iron, heavy metals, turbidity, conductivity, redox, temperature, and dissolved oxygen. Simultaneously with the in-situ measurements and sample collection described above, we also acquired representative water spectra using a UAV (Chalkidiki: 26 spectra; Kirki: 9 spectra).
- Sampling locations were selected using a stratified random design, considering proximity to mining sites, land use, and water flow patterns, while ensuring accessibility and safety.
- Accuracy assessment was conducted. Partial Least Square Regression (PLSR) analyses were used to compare EO-derived parameters with reference values. R^2 and RMSE were calculated for Suspended Solids and dissolved iron Cd and As.

Additional information

Accuracy Metrics Applied

The assessment focused on quantitative predictions rather than thematic classifications. As a result, no classification-based metrics such as overall accuracy, kappa coefficient, or F1-score were applied. Instead, model performance was evaluated using statistical measures including the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the root mean square error (RMSE), both calculated for calibration and validation datasets.

Uncertainty Management

Uncertainties were primarily addressed through strict input data quality control. This involved careful preprocessing and verification of both *in situ* and EO datasets to reduce statistical variation and minimize the impact of measurement errors on the modelling results.

Spatial and Temporal Alignment

Temporal alignment between EO and *in situ* data was ensured by synchronizing field measurements (ground truth) with drone data acquisition. Satellite data with the closest possible acquisition dates were selected to maintain temporal consistency.

Spatial alignment was achieved by linking field sampling locations to corresponding EO pixels. Only homogeneous areas with sufficient spatial extent—relative to the spatial resolution of the remote sensing data—were used for calibration and validation. This ensured that the EO-derived values accurately represent the conditions at the sampling sites.

Practical Challenges

Several practical challenges were encountered during the study. Due to the high cost of analytical measurements, only a limited number of samples could be collected. This required a carefully designed sampling strategy, prioritizing areas with representative material heterogeneity to ensure meaningful and reliable results despite the limited dataset.

Summary of Accuracy Assessment

The prediction of water suspended Solids and dissolved iron Cd and As contents using hyperspectral data can be done at quantitative level, for multispectral data semi-quantitative estimations can be achieved.

2.5 Accuracy assessment approach for the demonstrating MultiMiner application ground moisture monitoring

In order to support monitoring of dam stability and seepage and controlling dust emissions at a mine site, ground moisture (GM) modelling and retrieval are conducted using synthetic aperture radar (SAR) satellite data and airborne SAR images. Accuracy evaluation metrics are utilised to assess the performance of the regression models by measuring the difference between field-measured and predicted values. Many accuracy evaluation metrics are available for evaluating regression performance, but only a few are commonly used for GM estimation. The studies on GM retrieval provide several typical prediction accuracy evaluation metrics as the number of available *in situ* measurements is limited. Among different regression evaluation metrics, Coefficient of Determination (R^2), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) are used with a limited number of *in situ* monitoring sensors/stations (Entekhabi et al., 2010; Gruber, 2020; Hajdu et al., 2018, Hegazi et al. 2021, Ullmann et al., 2023).

A Product description regarding accuracy assessment

A1 Product description

The products for GM monitoring consist of raster maps with different spatial and temporal resolutions due to the use of different EO data types. The *in situ* data input for all products is the same. Further, we detail the expected mapping products and auxiliary outputs based on used imaging sensors and employed imaging modes in terms of penetration depth, spatial and temporal resolution (Table 13).

Table 13. Product description ground moisture monitoring.

Demonstration of ground moisture monitoring – product description				
Map type	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	<i>in situ</i> data	EO data
Raster	20 m	12 days for single orbit, production will be performed from each image over the stdy site for various orbits	GM VWC (see B2)	Sentinel 1
Raster	20 m	Ad-hoc, for each procured image	GM VWC (see B2)	ALOS-2 PALSAR-2
Raster	2–5 m	Ad-hoc, for each datatake	GM VWC (see B2)	Multifrequency SAR drone

A2 Accuracy requirements

The following description is a recommendation for GM monitoring regarding accuracy requirements. In general case, EO data signatures (primarily from SAR images at C- and L-bands along with auxiliary optical images) are used as predictor variables along with *in situ* GM measurements data which are used as the response (or target) variable to produce a GM map. Generally, regression modelling is employed to predict GM and determine the relationship between predictor variables and the response variable. The regression approach is favoured due to the fact that numerical *in situ* moisture data is a continuous response variable, which is used to generate the thematic map of GM prediction. In more

specific cases where so-called SAR-time-series-change-detection (STCD) algorithm similar to SMOSAR is used, retrieved soil moisture index is used as a predictor variable along with other auxiliary variables to improve prediction accuracy compared to baseline STCD method. Soil moisture indices retrieved from L-band SAR data using physics based approaches such as, e.g. WCM-based on modified Dubois method (Dubois et al., 1995), can be either used directly for reporting, or similarly used as predictor variables in sediment-specific regression model fitting task, to produce improved predictions.

Frequent revisits and wide geographical coverage are characteristics of C-band Sentinel-1 (Torres, 2012). ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 offers L-band SAR data, and NISAR will provide global L-band radar observations at high spatial resolution and better ground penetration than with C-band data. Multi-polarization drone SAR data at C-, L- and P-bands will also be acquired.

As GM is heterogenous in spatial and temporal dimension, several key aspects need to be considered when performing the accuracy assessment of GM products derived using SAR images. Spacing, spatial support and extent of *in situ* data, when calculating accuracy metrics for derived GM products, should be considered. For GM predictions based on microwave image products, also image footprint, spatial resolution and penetration depth are critical. Microwave signal penetration depends on signal wavelength such that longer waves have deeper penetration, and they quickly saturate with GM increase.

Spatial coverage: Existing approaches for GM retrieval enable production of GM products based on Sentinel-1 data only cover open non-vegetated areas, with land cover maps used in masking out vegetated/forested and urban areas (Wang and Gao, 2023). With L- and P-bands, GM retrieval can be possible over grasslands, even though data analytics and modelling approaches are more complicated. At the mine site, methodologies for several typical sediment/vegetation situations are developed and validated, whereas produced models and predictions can be applicable for similar land cover types.

Penetration depth: As penetration of microwave signal at L and C-bands varies from a few centimetres to tens of centimetres, depending on moisture level and sediment type, realistic estimates from satellite SAR signatures can be provided at depths 0–5 centimetres (Le Morvan et al., 2008). This is the depth, at which reference IoT capacitance probes are installed, enabling training of prediction models and validation of predictions.

Spatial resolution: While SAR sensors have instrument and imaging mode specific azimuth and range resolution, normally multilooking is performed in connection with image orthorectification. Furthermore, produced estimates from SAR products are aggregated to coarser mapping units to increase overall mapping accuracy. It is important to keep in mind that current products based on SAR images are normally available with acceptable accuracies at coarse spatial resolutions of 1 ha to 1 km² (Balenzano et al., 2021). Here, a high resolution retrieval with minimum mapping unit of 0.04–1 ha primarily should be aimed.

Temporal resolution: Production of GM estimates depends on timeliness of SAR data takes, with repeat cycles of 12–24 days of Sentinel-1 depending on location (12 days over Europe), and 14 days for ALOS PALSAR-2. When several Sentinel-1 orbits are used over northern areas, temporal resolution can improve to 3–6 days depending on location. Within MultiMiner, tasked and archived ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 images will be acquired on ad-hoc basis and could be used in GM map production. Additionally, ad-hoc campaign with drone-mounted multifrequency SAR instrument should be planned, with corresponding maps to be produced and validated with *in situ* measurements.

B Accuracy assessment inputs

B1 EO data input

Raster maps of GM using Sentinel-1, ALOS-2 PALSAR-2, possibly NISAR, and multifrequency SAR drone will be produced. Sensor resolutions are given in Table 14. Multifrequency SAR drone measurements will provide better spatial resolution and flexibility by providing the use of a variety of imaging geometries and modes, thus enabling better potential for SAR based modelling for GM retrieval.

Table 14. SAR data specification for ground moisture monitoring.

Ground moisture monitoring – Input EO data					
Sensor	type	Resolution			MMU
		Azimuth	Range	temporal	Detected area
Sentinel-1 (IW mode)	microwave	≈ 5 m	≈ 20 m	12/24 days repeat cycle	0.04 – 1 ha
ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 (stripmap)	microwave	≈ 3 m	≈ 7 m	14 days repeat cycle	0.04 – 1 ha
Multi-Polarization drone SAR	microwave	< 2 m	< 2 m	Ad-hoc	0.04 – 1 ha

B2 *In situ* data input

The *in situ* GM measurements (at appr. 3–5 cm depth), listed in Table 15, are conducted at 4 different locations, each representing separate sediment textural class. The sites having vegetation cover are expected to have successful moisture retrieval with L- and P-band data, whereas C-band may assist in surface moisture retrieval of bare sediment covered sites. An electrical capacitance probe, percometer (Plakk, 1994) is used to measure the soil bulk dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r). Dielectric permittivity is highly sensitive to the soil water content, which can be calculated from the ϵ_r measurement data using suitable calibration equation.

Table 15. *In situ* data specification for ground moisture monitoring.

Ground moisture monitoring in Ihalainen site – <i>In situ</i> data	
Ground moisture (GM) measurements from <i>in situ</i> capacitance probes	Point measurements at 5 cm depth, frequent measurements with temporal sampling of approx. 1 hour over several locations
Soil bulk dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r) using a capacitance probe	Provides measurements of dielectric value indicative of volumetric soil moisture content, measured during dedicated field campaigns using a capacitance probe
Sediment level small-area estimates	Calculated using point measurements of GM and dielectric permittivity for homogeneous areas composed of a single sediment textural type

C Sampling design evaluation

The spatial distribution and relatively low number of soil moisture sensors do not allow classical random sampling in the spatial domain (with or without stratification), or even balanced training/test sets for model training and accuracy assessment. This is typical situation for GM studies. However, the approach could be stratified random sampling, where 2–3 permanent *in situ* sensors are installed within each sediment textural class using random spatial location within each sediment. A physical calibration of the GM sensors both in the field (with capacitance probe) and in the lab with soil sample analysis can be done to obtain more reliable reference data for GM modelling. Figure 3 represents the map of Ihalainen mine and the location of the field measured points.

Figure 3. A map of Ihalainen mine. The red triangles indicate places soil moisture sensors are located, and the blue points indicate where dielectric permittivity and electrical conductivity measurements were taken by the hand-held percometer.

D Accuracy measurement recommendation

With information from product description, accuracy assessment inputs and sampling design a good practice for accuracy measurements is described in the following.

The recommendation is to follow a standard approach using the accuracy measures calculated using satellite image -based predictions versus *in situ* measured point measurements (see e.g. Entekhabi et al., 2010). What is new in this approach, compared to methods commonly used in SAR based GM retrievals (Gruber, 2020), is the potential to calculate small area estimates for various time instances and quantify the associated uncertainty of the *in situ* data. This is possible thanks to abundance of data measured in temporal domain using fixed *in situ* capacitance probes, even though these measurements are limited in spatial domain (2–3 *in situ* sensors for each sediment type). In this way, it will be possible to perform a more detailed uncertainty analysis, as overall variance represents a combination of sampling variance and residual variance due to model fitting.

E Accuracy assessment actually performed

Implementation Status

The planned accuracy assessment was implemented partially, using reference data from installed IoT soil moisture sensors, and ad-hoc reference soil moisture measurements during one-time drone-SAR campaign.

Selected EO Data Sources

Initial work focused on evaluating soil moisture retrievals from multi-temporal Sentinel-1 C-band SAR data using time series physics-based and machine learning retrieval models. Complementary experiment with multifrequency SAR drone (P, L, C bands) were performed at Ihalainen site during campaign in June 2024. L-band ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 data were acquired and retrievals were performed with physics based and machine learning methods at more limited scale as the number of observations was more limited. PALSAR-2 image acquisitions still continue and will be completed end of 2025.

Sentinel-1 IW mode, dual-pol (VV, VH), 10-20 m spatial resolution, 6–12 day temporal resolution, acquisitions between 2023–2024. With multiple image datatakes, initial accuracy assessment included approximately 330 observations.

Drone-SAR campaigns were used to produce estimates at a spatial resolution <10 m, even though native resolution was somewhat better, however extensive multi-looking was needed to compensate relatively poor radiometric quality, with number of observations limited to <50 corresponding to actually performed measurements during the field campaign, with portable percometer.

Processing, Calibration, and Integration of *In Situ* Measurements with EO Data

Measurements were calibrated against gravimetric soil samples from Ihalainen site, averaged to match the SAR pixel footprint, and co-registered with Sentinel-1 acquisitions. DroneSAR reference grids were downscaled to common resolution for integration. Integration with EO data was performed using several machine learning and physics-based modelling frameworks to establish a set of prediction models to produce high resolution SAR data-based estimates of soil moisture.

Statistical Measures Applied

R^2 , RMSE, and MAE were calculated at plot level (radius 15 meter from IoT sensor installation point) between model predictions and sensor-recorder reference values. Additionally, sediment level and coarser area level (small area) estimates were computed.

Additional information

Additional Accuracy Metrics

Relative RMSE and sediment-level and coarser-mapping-unit level (small area) estimates were computed, in addition to plot-level estimates.

Applied Validation Methods

K-fold cross-validation (k=5) was used as the number of reference observations was limited

Treatment of Uncertainties

The regression modelling inherently accounted for observational noise through residual analysis, and care was taken to avoid overfitting (systematic train/test splits and regularization). No dedicated

uncertainty propagation framework was applied, but sources of error such as sampling variance, probe calibration limits, SAR speckle, and co-registration mismatch are acknowledged. These were treated implicitly as part of the model residuals rather than being quantified separately.

Final Reference Data Points

30-300 based on sensor modality and experiment.

Ensuring Balanced Representation Across Sediment Textures and Land Cover Types

Reference points were selected to cover primary soil texture classes in the study site areas: organic blacksoils, clay-dominated and flotation sands.

Evaluation of the Representativeness of the Reference Data

Reference points were selected to cover a range of soil textures, topographic and land cover conditions at the study site, which provided basic diversity in the observed and reference datasets. Use of permanently installed IoT soil moisture sensors allowed to capture diverse wet and dry reference observations, including extremes, in a consistent manner, leading to a diverse and temporally representative domain of reference measurements. However, for wide-area mapping the spatial distribution of installed sensors remained somewhat limited, thus examined models can't be readily used on other types of soils and land cover (or used with care, requiring potential model finetuning).

Criteria and Tolerances for Spatial and Temporal Alignment Between EO Acquisitions and Field Measurements

Simultaneous (within couple hours) alignment between EO datatakes and reference measurements were carried out due to sensitivity of soil moisture dynamics to environmental effects.

Practical Challenges Encountered

Limitations typical to the application were encountered. Dense vegetation and taller grass conditions introduced additional components in SAR backscatter. DroneSAR deployments were constrained by weather and site accessibility, as well as operational costs and potential technical issues, leading to limited assessment.

Summary of Accuracy Assessment

Key Outcomes of the Comparison Between EO Products and Reference Data

SAR-based soil moisture retrievals (in presence of auxiliary data layers, such as land cover or optical, topography layers) demonstrated moderate to strong correlations with the *in situ* measurements ($R^2 = 0.45-0.65$ depending on site and season). RMSE values were typically 5-8% units on plot level, reducing to 3-4% for small area estimates. Multifrequency droneSAR assessment was limited, with initial results indicating that multifrequency fusion is instrumental in improving soil moisture prediction accuracy.

Main Uncertainties and Identified Limitations

Such limitations were observed:

- Limited number of *in situ* campaigns restricts assessment of potential of droneSAR instruments;

- Absence of suitable L-band satellites restrict soil moisture retrieval potential, especially potential of C+L-band SAR data fusion – with launched NISAR (in July 2025) this is likely to change and better results can be obtained, also including denser vegetated soils
- probe saturation at high VWC values adds noise;
- spatial representativeness of reference points was ensured across several studied soil types, but not across all possible combinations of land cover, vegetation and soil textures, which limits potential of wide-area mapping with derived models.

Overall Reliability of the Produced Soil Moisture Maps for Monitoring and Decision-Making in the MultiMiner Project

Despite limitations, the satellite and drone SAR based soil moisture estimates provide a consistent and interpretable picture of wetting/drying patterns at mine sites and surrounding areas. They are sufficiently reliable for monitoring trends, detecting anomalies, and supporting initial environmental risk assessments.

2.6 Accuracy assessment approach for the demonstrating MultiMiner application integrated tailings storage facility monitoring

The original purpose of the task was to monitor the composition of material accumulating in a tailings storage facility (TSF) and to track the three-dimensional shape of the area over time aiming to create a 3D/4D TSF model. Changes in the participating industry partners in the consortium resulted in a change also in the planned TSF study site and consequently modifications in the task goals.

The current study site is a decommissioned TSF site at Olympias, Chalkidiki, Greece, from which material is being removed by Hellas Gold in 2016-2025 (Lopez-Pacheco, 2025). The goal is to monitor if the TSF removal has reached the substrate sediment in the area since excavation of the TSF sediments started in 2016.

Instead of monitoring, the task has focused on identifying areas containing tailings material versus areas where tailings have already been removed, based on EO and *in situ* data. Using the collected data, the current goal is to create a 3D visualization, without the monitoring aspect. The current 3D visualization approach combines mineralogical composition of the TSF surface sediment and its digital elevation model (DEM) in one instance of time. However, once high to medium spatial resolution hyperspectral satellite data will be available from satellite platforms and high resolution DEMs were produced from satellite InSAR data, the presented approach could be operational for TSF rehabilitation monitoring. Alternatively, temporal drone hyperspectral imaging and DEM generation could be done for monitoring of the rehabilitation process.

A Product description regarding accuracy assessment

A1 Product description

The integrated TSF monitoring -application used hyperspectral UAV and satellite data and *in situ* data. The resulting products are described in Table 16. Data interpretation links them to a single 3D visualization of the TSF. Hyperspectral RS provides the information on the mineralogy and UAV photogrammetry was used to quantify the elevation surface.

Table 16. Product description Integrated TSF monitoring.

Demonstration of integrated TSF monitoring – product description			
Map/Description	DEM	Volume Change Map	Mineralogy map/ Mineral composition map
<i>In situ</i> data	UAV data	UAV data	Tailings samples
EO data			UAV HSI data EnMAP
classes/ segments	continuous	continuous	classification

The mineral mapping results generated by wavelength mapper in MultiMiner Miner Mapper software and Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) and Linear Spectral Unmixing (LSU). Their 3D visualization was done with ArcGIS Pro software. The mineral mapping results (output as a raster layer) were draped over the digital surface model (DSM) and visualized with Local Scene viewing capabilities.

A2 Accuracy requirements

The following description represents a recommended framework for TSF monitoring. The characteristics of the TSF are observed *in situ* only once by ground-based sampling to gather information on the mineralogy and chemistry to verify EO hyperspectral data. Parallel a photogrammetric survey is performed to characterize the 3D surface topography of the TSF.

In situ measurements are needed for validation of the model.

The EO hyperspectral data have to be orthorectified and geocoded with an accuracy of 1-2 pixels in order to match the the UAV spectral and data interpretation with the sediment/tailings sample locations. The accuracy of the used GPS system to record the location of the sampling stations was 3m.

B Accuracy assessment inputs

B1 EO data input

The photogrammetric UAV data acquisition was performed together with hyperspectral UAV flights during one field campaign. Further photogrammetry measurements were provided by the industry partner Hellas Gold and consisted of RGB UAV flights (Table 17).

Table 17. EO and UAV data input – Integrated TSF monitoring.

Integrated TSF monitoring – Input EO and UAV data				
	Datatype	Spatial resolution	Aquisition frequency	Time period covered (year)
Sentinel-2	Multispectral	10–20 m	Multiple acquisitions per year	2020–2025
EnMAP/ EMIT	Hyperspectral	30 m/60 m	Aiming for multiple acquisitions per year	2019 2 times in 2021 2023 2024,2025
Hyperspectral and photogrammetric drone data	Hyperspectral and photogrammetry	few cm	Once	2024

B2 *In situ* data input

In situ data (Table 18) for integrated TSF monitoring are measured on site with varying approaches. Spectrometers are used for spectral characterisation of the *in situ* setting. Samples are taken for latter analysis to be conducted in laboratory. For a detailed description of the *in situ* data see *D4.1 Part 1 MultiMiner Field Guidebook*.

Table 18. Input *in situ* data for integrated TSF monitoring.

Integrated TSF monitoring - Input <i>in situ</i> data		
Variable	Ground truth sampling	<i>In situ</i> measurements HSI
Mineralogy	Sediment/soil samples	Field spectrometry
Chemistry	Sediment/soil samples	Field spectrometry

C Sampling design evaluation

Regarding the product type of 3D TSF monitoring and the characteristics of input EO data and *in situ* reference data, following practices for sampling design are suggested.

- simple random sampling
- cluster sampling

A simple random sampling scheme could be applied due to the highly variable surface characteristics. Cluster sampling was carried out to ensure the most representative sample of the observed sample site. It provides a possibility for calibration purpose of the HS UAV data takes since this cluster information can be used as validation of spectrally derived mineralogical information.

In situ reference data consist of one ground truth campaign with sediment sampling for laboratory analysis (spectral, mineralogy, chemistry) for validation of the EO data.

D Accuracy measurement recommendation

The hyperspectral data are validated via *in situ* data (ground truth sampling) which were mineralogical described by XRD and field spectroscopy. As the number of *in situ* sample sites within the MultiMiner project are limited, reference data are limited.

SAM and LSU fundamentally generate different outputs. Therefore, their accuracy needs to be evaluated using method-specific metrics. SAM produces single mineral category per sampling location, while LSU predicts mineral abundances. XRD-derived mineralogy is used as a reference data for evaluation.

SAM assigns one mineral class per sample, while XRD basically indicates the presence of multiple mineral phases within the same sample. It is necessary to make outputs comparable by converting XRD mineral properties to presence/absence information, for example using a predefined threshold. For each sample, the SAM classification is considered correct if the assigned mineral corresponds to any mineral identified as present by XRD. Therefore, the classification performance is evaluated using:

Sample-level accuracy: The proportion of samples for which the SAM-assigned class matches an XRD-present mineral.

Per-mineral precision: For each mineral, the proportion of SAM assignments that are confirmed as present by XRD. This metric highlights minerals that are reliably identified versus those that are frequently over-predicted.

Accuracy assessment of LSU (abundance-based): LSU predicts mineral fractional abundances and can be quantitatively compared with XRD-derived mineral outputs as volume percentages.

Therefore, LSU performance can be quantified by using: MAE, to measure the average absolute deviations from XRD results.

Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to evaluate the strength and direction of the linear relationship between LSU-derived mineral fractional abundances and the corresponding XRD-derived mineral proportions for each mineral.

E Accuracy assessment actually performed

Implementation Status

- A ground truth campaign was conducted on September 16, 2024 at the Olympias TSF, Chalkidiki, Greece. A total of 12 sediment/tailings samples were collected, equally distributed between two subareas: one where tailings were still present and one where tailings had already been removed.
- Sampling was carried out according to GTK's internal operational guidelines, including the Geochemical Operations Manual, Fieldwork Manual, and Fieldwork Hazard Identification Checklist. The team also attended the Health & Safety Induction Meeting organized by Hellas Gold before sampling.
- The collected samples were analyzed in GTK's laboratory using X-ray diffraction (XRD) Rietveld method and, for selected samples, complemented by field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) analysis. In total, 17 semi-quantitative phase composition analyses were conducted, covering both bulk (12) and fine fractions (5). Three samples underwent FE-SEM phase identification to further refine the interpretation of mineralogical phases.
- The mineralogical analyses followed strict laboratory protocols with quality assurance through controlled preparation, standardized methods, regular instrument maintenance and internal validation samples.
- Reported challenges included: (i) difficulties in precisely aligning sample points with drone flight areas, (ii) changes in field surface topography compared to satellite imagery, (iii) the challenge of sampling was to get the sample as close to the surface as possible so that the sample material could match the surface composition analyzed by the UAV hyperspectral, (iiii) the need to maintain safe distances from ongoing machinery operations and steep slopes, and (iiiii) uncertainty about dust from excavation and traffic on the ground, how it affects UAV hyperspectral results.
- The GTK standardized procedure for consistency and reliability in sampling and laboratory analysis XRD and SEM analysis was followed.
- The field spectral data were collected, and a white calibration platform was used to calibrate the measurements. Used data for integrated EO Data Sources: UAV photogrammetry, UAV hyperspectral
- Statistical Measures Calculated and Their Resulting Performance Metrics: MAE and Pearson correlation coefficient (r).

Additional information

Additional accuracy metrics calculated beyond RMSE, RPD, and R^2 :

- The good quality field spectral data are used for verification of the mineral spectral features against the USGS spectral library 7.0 and the XRD data. Relevant spectral wavelength features of the field spectra are calculated and plotted against the XRD mineralogical abundances.

- Three data processing approaches are taken for mineralogical interpretation of the UAV hyperspectral data, namely Wavelength Mapper, Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM), Linear Spectral Unmixing (LSU).
 - In case of using the hyperspectral UAV data, which has limited spectral quality due to partial cloud cover during the acquisition, the Wavelength mapping results are considered exploratory in nature. In the data the spectral features of minerals cannot be distinguished clearly because of high signal-to-noise-ratio. For example, a feature at around 2330-2340 nm can be caused by two different mineral groups, namely carbonate and chlorite thus these minerals cannot be spectrally separated using the spectral feature. Thus, the output maps of the spectral features will only be verified qualitatively against the exposed sediment type on the 12 field sampling stations, i.e. cleaned sites vs. TSF sediments.
 - The output of the SAM is categorical indicating the dominant spectrally active mineral in a pixel, whereas XRD provides quantitative mineral proportions. This fundamental difference makes the use of a confusion matrix inappropriate, as reducing XRD results to a single dominant mineral oversimplifies the data and can produce misleading accuracy metrics.
 - On the contrary, LSU outputs the fractional abundance of each chosen mineral in a pixel. The result will be validated against the abundances of the individual minerals from XRD analysis. MAE, and r values will be calculated.
- Validation Methods Applied for Model Performance Assessment: The XRD results are not used as inputs to SAM and LSU. Thus, all 12 samples can be used for validation.
 - Validation and Quality Assurance of Mineralogical Analyses
 - The accuracy and quality of the mineralogical analyses were ensured by using two different methods, XRD and FE-SEM, which rely on different techniques for phase identification. Based on the analyses, the phase identification was semi-quantitatively successful, as the phases of the samples were mostly consistent with each other using both methods. The challenge for these methods is to identify very fine nano-scale, mass-like or amorphous glassy material. Some phases in the samples occur as these mass-like compounds, making their precise identification or naming in the context of the project impossible.

Summary of Accuracy Assessment

The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and mean absolute error (MAE) were used to evaluate the agreement between LSU estimates and XRD measurements for each mineral (see Table 19).

Biotite exhibits strong agreement ($r = 0.84$), while calcite ($r = 0.76$) and dolomite ($r = 0.67$) show moderate agreement. Kaolinite ($r = 0.28$) and illite ($r = 0.18$) have a weak positive correlation with the XRD measurements, whereas rhodochrosite ($r = -0.33$), and goethite ($r = -0.46$) have weak or negative correlations.

The reason for comparatively poor performance of some minerals could be that the drone-based hyperspectral imaging data was obtained in partially cloud shadowed illumination, which led to distorted spectral features and a lower signal-to-noise ratio. In addition, the discrepancies may arise

by differences between the ideal reference spectra from the USGS library and the drone-based hyperspectral imaging spectra.

Table 19. Accuracy assessment of LSU-based mineral abundance identification using XRD results as reference.

Mineral	r	MAE
Kaolinite	0.22	27.44
Calcite	0.76	2.37
Dolomite	0.67	2.11
Illite	0.18	10.23
Rhodochrosite	-0.33	11.03
Goethite	-0.46	1.83
Biotite	0.84	0.98

2.7 Accuracy assessment approach for the demonstrating MultiMiner application dam stability monitoring and open pit stability monitoring

Mining operations can compromise the stability of open pit slopes, and dam walls may likewise be susceptible to failure. To maintain operational safety, geodetic monitoring techniques such as laser scanning and GNSS are routinely applied, but these methods are expensive. In contrast, InSAR provides a cost-effective alternative due to freely available satellite data and near ready-to-use products such as the European Ground Motion Service (EGMS). Despite this advantage, interpreting InSAR data remains challenging for non-experts, particularly in cold regions where winter data gaps complicate displacement analysis. The subtasks aim to develop a semi-automated workflow designed to improve the usability of EGMS data under such conditions, thereby enhancing the reliability of InSAR-based monitoring for mine-safety decision-making. The workflow's accuracy is evaluated in three stages: assessing the reliability of the InSAR displacement measurements, detecting and filtering measurement points affected by phase-unwrapping errors, and validating whether the resulting deformation clusters correspond to actual causative processes—anthropogenic, geophysical, or geological.

A Product description regarding accuracy assessment

A1 Product description

The updated EGMS L2A dataset, serves as the primary source for assessing ground stability at both the dam and the open-pit site. This dataset provides time-series LOS displacement measurements derived from Sentinel-1 acquisitions, with winter periods excluded. Although average annual displacement rates are provided, the exclusion of winter data may limit their significance for monitoring stability. Particularly for the dam, where the primary concern is detecting structural failure or wall breaches, displacement trends are best analyzed and tracked through the full time series rather than annualized averages.

A2 Accuracy requirements

The accuracy of InSAR-derived displacement estimates is affected by several factors, including decorrelation and atmospheric noise. For EGMS data, the workflow includes strict quality control, and products are accompanied by reliability indicators such as temporal coherence and RMSE. Additionally, temporal sampling and the number of available SAR acquisitions influence measurement reliability, which explains the absence of descending orbit data at the Ihalainen site.

When both ascending and descending datasets are available, they serve as a cross-validation tool for assessing displacement accuracy. While accuracy requirements depend on the application, the noise level remains the most significant factor for interpretation. Consequently, displacement values must be evaluated in relation to this noise using metrics like temporal coherence or RMSE. Finally, the spatial distribution of measurement points is critical; a single point is insufficient to infer ground movement, and interpretation should instead rely on the consistent behavior of neighboring points.

B Accuracy assessment inputs

B1 EO data input

The input data for the workflow is summarized in Table 20. For the selected test site, EGMS data is available only for the ascending orbit. To complement the EGMS product and facilitate cross-validation, additional in-house InSAR processing was performed using the same acquisition dates as the EGMS dataset. Furthermore, displacement data from the descending orbit, which is not included in the EGMS dataset was also processed, as detailed in Table 20.

Table 20. summary of EO data source for both the SLC and EGMS L2A data

Demonstration of integrated of open pit and dam stability monitoring – Input EO data				
Orbit direction	Path	Total acquisitions	Period	Data type
Ascending	014	131	2019.04.07- 2023.10.31	L2A time series & SLC
Ascending	087	129	2019.04.12-2023.10.24	L2A time series & SLC
Descending	007	58	2021.05.26-2024.10.13	SLC

B2 In situ data input

The in-situ data used for the accuracy assessment was the GNSS dataset provided by the industry partner, Nordkalk. This dataset consists of processed campaign measurements, which include final coordinates corresponding to the observation dates. The temporal sampling and spatial coverage of the dataset are presented in Table 21 and Figure 4.

Table 21. GNSS campaign data acquisitions – frequency of observations per year per station

Demonstration of integrated of open pit and dam stability monitoring – Insitu data					
GNSS	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
RA1	2	1	1	2	1
RA2	2	1	0	0	0
RA3	1	2	1	1	1
RA4	1	2	1	1	1
RA5	1	1	1	0	1
RA6	1	2	1	1	1
RA7	1	2	1	1	1
RA8	1	2	0	1	1
RA9	1	2	0	1	1
RA10	1	2	0	1	1
RA12	1	2	0	1	1
RA13	1	1	1	1	1
RA14	1	1	1	1	1
RA15	2	1	1	1	1
RA16	1	1	1	1	1
RA17	1	1	1	1	1

Figure 4. Locations of the campaign GNSS stations

C Sampling design evaluation

The ideal situation is to have as many GNSS points as possible, preferably operating as continuous CORS stations. However, due to cost constraints, the number of GNSS points is typically limited and may be campaign-based rather than permanent, as is the case at our test site. Regarding spatial and temporal sampling, we used all the data provided and therefore had no control over the sampling design since these are historical observations. The initial GNSS dataset spans from 2017 to 2023; however, we restricted our analysis to the period between 2019 and 2023 to ensure temporal overlap with the Sentinel-1 data. It can be seen that most of the stations were observed with a low frequency, either once or twice per year, with some stations not being observed at all in certain year(s). For a direct comparison with the EGMS LOS measurements, the GNSS 3D coordinates were converted into a 1D LOS. This was necessary because the EGMS data for the descending-pass is unavailable at Ihalainen site due to a limited number of Sentinel-1 images. The datasets were temporally aligned by averaging two Sentinel-1 acquisitions closest to each GNSS observation date, and this averaged data was then referenced to the first GNSS observation date within the shared temporal window. Similarly, a 20-meter buffer zone was created around each GNSS station and the median measuring point within this buffer was selected to represent the localized ground displacement.

D Accuracy measurement recommendation

The conventional approach is to have permanent GNSS stations so that Sentinel-1 acquisition dates can be directly matched with GNSS observations, and, when possible, the decomposed InSAR east and west components can be compared with GNSS rather than with LOS measurements. Unfortunately, at our site only LOS data are available, and the GNSS dataset consists solely of campaign measurements with low temporal sampling. Ideally, GNSS stations should also be located in a stable area, or at least in an area with known displacement, so they can serve as a reference point, since InSAR provides relative measurements. In such cases, comparison metrics such as standard deviation or RMSE can be used to evaluate the accuracy of the InSAR measurements relative to the in-situ GNSS data.

E Accuracy assessment actually performed Implementation Status

During the accuracy assessment, it was found that the campaign-based GNSS data could not be used as reliable in-situ reference data. As shown in Figure 5, the overall agreement between the GNSS measurements and the InSAR LOS measurements was poor.

Figure 5. Comparison of InSAR and GNSS LOS measurements at selected points as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 6. A comparison of average LOS velocity measurements: (a) EGMS processing vs. (b) our own processing.

Considering the poor agreement between GNSS and EGMS and the lack of descending EGMS data at Ihalainen to provide a check and redundancy, we did our own independent PS processing using the same Sentinel-1 image acquisitions that were used as input for the EGMS processing. It should however

be noted that the EGMS processing chain is subjected to a high level of checks that includes quality assurance and control (Kotzerke, Siegmund, & Larsen, 2024). In addition, they also conduct validation on selected sites. Unfortunately, these sites do not fall within our study area, but it has been demonstrated that EGMS products are of high quality (Koudogbo, et al., 2025). Moreover, the EGMS products are accompanied by noise metrics such as temporal coherence and RMSE. Therefore, by conducting a parallel processing chain, the motivation wasn't entirely about accuracy assessment. Instead, it was to provide an independent check with fine-tuned parameters, such as temporal coherence, and to generally provide a comparison and redundancy. Figure 6 shows that average displacement rate for both the EGMS and our own processing. Both are filtered with the same temporal coherence of 0.55, which was the temporal coherence threshold in our PS processing.

Furthermore, temporal domain comparison at specific locations within the tailings dam and open pit as depicted in Figure 7. The chosen points are situated in areas of the dam and open pit that are characterized by significant displacement either toward or away from the satellite's LOS. We have also included comparisons from a location outside the dam and open pit that do not show any significant movement.

Figure 7. LOS time series comparison between EGMS processing and our own processing for points marked in Figure 6. The time series corresponds to the median of the measuring points within a 20-meter buffer around the selected points, as indicated in Figure 6.

In addition to our own InSAR processing, we also generated another set of accuracy-assessment data consisting of simulated InSAR data that reflects the displacement trends observed in the EGMS dataset, as shown in Table 22. This simulated dataset was used to evaluate the performance of the approach we developed for detecting unwrapping errors in the EGMS data, which are associated with large data gaps during winter. The purpose of the simulated InSAR was not to assess the accuracy of the displacement measurements themselves, but to provide a benchmark for evaluating the detection method. Since the number of measurement points affected by unwrapping errors is known in advance, the detected errors can be compared against this reference using a false-truth-rate-based evaluation.

Table 22. Summary of trends of the simulated InSAR Measuring Points

Demonstration of integrated of open pit and dam stability monitoring – simulated data		
Case	Trend Type	Contain steps
Noise only	None	None
Continuous trend + noise	Continuous	None
Mixed trend, no trend, & Steps	Intermittent	Yes
Seasonal steps + noise	None	Yes
Intermittent trend + random steps	Intermittent	Yes
Continuous trend + random steps	Continuous	Yes

Summary of Accuracy Assessment

A comparison of GNSS measurements with PS measurements revealed poor agreement, characterized by large RMSE values and, in some instances, opposing temporal trends. The discrepancy can be attributed to limited temporal sampling of GNSS campaign data, a maximum of two observations per year compared with the 30 Sentinel-1 images. Other contributing factors include a lack of one-to-one spatial overlap, since PS measurements average within a 20-meter buffer around each GNSS station. Similarly, the absence of EGMS descending data prevented validation of horizontal and vertical components and restricted the comparisons to only LOS, introducing additional uncertainties during conversion. In addition, processing uncertainties inherent to each measurement method further exacerbate the misfit. The observed lack of fit between GNSS and EGMS data does not undermine the usability of EGMS measurements for monitoring deformation in open pits and dam stability, as the discrepancy arises from data mismatch rather than limitations in EGMS data quality. Furthermore, the reliability of PS-based measurements is well established in the literature and is reinforced by EGMS's own quality assessment, control, and validation reports (Kotzerke, Siegmund, & Larsen, 2024; Koudogbo, et al., 2025) which collectively demonstrate the robustness of its processing methodology. Although the available EGMS data limits the analysis to one-dimensional displacement and prevents clear identification of movement direction, this limitation was addressed by processing descending Sentinel-1 images. These images, despite lacking temporal overlap with the ascending data, still provide useful insights into slope dynamics. An additional limitation we also observed in the EGMS dataset is the presence of unwrapping artifacts in certain measuring points, which result in apparent movement being recorded only during winter months. This was, however, mitigated by identifying and excluding the affected points from the analysis. Accordingly, the use of EGMS data remains viable within the MultiMiner project, although supplementary post-processing may be required to address residual unwrapping effects and the spatial heterogeneity of the measuring points.

2.8 Definition of the accuracy assessment approach for the demonstrating MultiMiner application dust monitoring

Commonly used accuracy assessment methods for dust monitoring using EO data and methods include ground truth data collection. This method involves collecting data from ground-based monitoring stations to compare against satellite observations. Ground truth data can include measurements of dust concentration, particle size distribution, and other relevant parameters. Comparing satellite-derived dust monitoring data with reference data from established monitoring networks or ground-based instruments provides the means for quantifying the product accuracy. Assessing the spatial and temporal variability of dust monitoring data can help to identify areas of high uncertainty or potential errors. Analysing patterns and trends in the data can provide insights into the accuracy of the monitoring methods.

A Product description regarding accuracy assessment

A1 Product description

Common products for dust monitoring using EO data and methods include atmospheric dust concentration mapping, where concentration of dust particles in the atmosphere can be predicted. This can help identify areas with high levels of dust pollution and assess the impact on air quality.

Dust transport modelling based on EO data can be used to track the spatial transport patterns of dust particles across long distances. This information is crucial for understanding global dust distribution patterns and their effects on climate and ecosystems.

With EO data also deposition of dust particles on land (e.g., vegetation) and water bodies can be monitored. This data is important for assessing the environmental impact of dust pollution on ecosystems and human health.

In the MultiMiner project five different raster maps will be created (Table 23). Using different types of EO data and *in situ* data, dust sources, dust on vegetation, vegetation stress and dust transport is highlighted.

Table 23. Product description dust monitoring.

Demonstration of dust monitoring – product description – raster maps					
Spatial resolution	temporal resolution	<i>in situ</i> data	EO data	sample unit/distribution	classes/segments
30 and 60 m	one date	substrate samples - XRD	PRISMA/EMIT	random	classification/dust source
30 and 60 m	multitemporal (if possible)	element composition, mineral composition	PRISMA/EMIT	spatially dispersed sampling	continous variable, classification/Dust on vegetation
10–20 m	multitemporal	element composition,	Sentinel-2	spatially dispersed sampling	dust on vegetation

		mineral composition			
70 m	multitemporal	monitoring data https://environmental.hellas-gold.com/	ECOSTRESS	set monitoring network	vegetation stress
1 km; 3 km; 8,5 km	multitemporal	monitoring data https://environmental.hellas-gold.com/	MCD19A2 - MODIS/Terra+ Aqua Land Aerosol Optical Depth; SEVIRI/METEO SAT; 10CAMS	A set monitoring network	dust transport

A2 Accuracy requirements

When it comes to the product accuracy requirements for dust monitoring using EO data and methods, there are several key factors to consider. The product should have a high spatial resolution to accurately detect and monitor dust particles in the atmosphere. This means that the product should be able to distinguish small-scale features and phenomena related to dust sources and transport. Timeliness is essential for dust monitoring, as dust events can be transient and rapidly evolving. The product should provide frequent updates to capture changes in dust concentrations over time. Different dust particles have unique spectral characteristics that can be detected using specific wavelengths. The product should have a sufficient spectral resolution to differentiate between dust particles and other atmospheric components. It also should provide accurate estimations of dust concentration levels in the atmosphere. This requires calibration and validation of the EO data using ground-based measurements and other reference sources. To ensure the reliability of the product, validation and quality control processes should be implemented. This involves comparing the product with ground truth data and conducting inter-comparison with other relevant products.

By meeting these accuracy requirements, products for dust monitoring using EO data and methods can provide valuable insights into dust emissions, transport patterns, and their impacts on the environment and human health.

B Accuracy assessment inputs

B1 EO data input

Table 24 summarizes the used EO data for dust monitoring.

Table 24. EO data specifications used for dust monitoring.

Dust monitoring – Input EO data					
	Sensor	Resolution			MMU
	optical	spatial	spectral	temporal	Detected area

EMIT	Hyperspectral VNIR/SWIR	60 m	450–2500 nm	irregular	Whole defined AOI
PRISMA	Hyperspectral VNIR/SWIR	30 n	450–2500 nm	irregular	Whole defined AOI
ECOSTRESS	Thermal/Vegetation stress ready-to-use products	70 m		multitemporal	Whole defined AOI
MCD19A2 - MODIS/Terra+Aqua Land Aerosol Optical Depth	Optical/ Aerosol Optical Depth ready-to-use products	1 km		multitemporal	Whole defined AOI
SEVIRI/METEOSAT	Thermal/Dust product	3 km		multitemporal	Whole defined AOI
CAMS	Air quality reanalysis and forecasting	8.5 km		multitemporal	Whole defined AOI

B2 In situ data input

Specifications of *in situ* data input acquired at Chalkidiki and Ihalainen are shown in Table 25 and in Figure 8.

Table 25. In situ data specifications for dust monitoring.

Dust monitoring – Input <i>in situ</i> data		
	Chalkidiki	Ihalainen
Dust traps: dust composition	samples: 9 (3 around each mining site) PM10, PM2.5, Fe, heavy metals, element composition, mineral composition)	samples 3 (3 around 1 mining site) element composition, mineral composition
Data from monitoring networks or stations	IEMS: primarily PM10 and PM2.5 11 monitoring stations (Figure 8)	5 monitoring stations https://ekilmanlaatu.net/

Figure 8. Dust monitoring stations in Chalkidiki (IEMS)- overview.

C Sampling design evaluation

When designing a sampling plan for dust monitoring using EO data and methods, there are general requirements to consider:

For the accuracy assessment primarily the monitoring data provided by the existing monitoring systems/stations are used. When extending the research to the amount of dust and dust composition (mineral composition, heavy metal content), dust traps are installed in a close proximity to the mine

(3 stations per mine site) at 3 different directions (Figure 9). This design can be described as a spatially dispersed sampling approach and it allows a collection of dust particles at various points around the mine site, providing a more representative sample of airborne particulate matter in the area. By having sampling stations placed in different directions, potential sources and patterns of dust dispersion can be better identified and characterized.

The last criteria for selecting the position of the dust traps should be the accessibility on one site. On the other hand, it should be ensured that the dust traps are far enough not to be interfered with the traffic pollution originating outside of a mine site.

Figure 9. Dust traps at Chalkidiki area- left: dust traps location overview – right: examples of dust traps installed in the field.

D Accuracy measurement recommendation

Some recommendations for accuracy measurement regarding monitoring dust emissions using the EO data are described in the following section. Statistical analysis should be performed to quantify the accuracy of the dust monitoring measurements. Metrics such as RMSE could be computed to assess the level of agreement between the EO data and ground truth measurements. A cross-validation with multiple sources of EO data and methods could be used to compare the results. Comparing the outputs from different sources would help in identifying any discrepancies and improving the accuracy of the measurements.

E Accuracy assessment actually performed

Selected EO Data Sources

The EO data specifications actually used for dust monitoring are shown in Table 26.

Table 26. EO data specifications used for dust monitoring (accuracy assessments actually performed).

Demonstration of dust monitoring – EO data		
Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	EO data
30 and 60 m	multitemporal (if possible)	PRISMA/EnMAP/ EMIT
10–20 m	multitemporal	Sentinel-2
1 km; 3 km; 8,5 km	multitemporal	MCD19A2 - MODIS/Terra+Aqua Land Aerosol Optical Depth; SEVIRI/METEOSAT; 10CAMS
25 cm	One-day	PIKA-L (hyperspectral, UAV)

Produced Raster Map Products

- SPATIO-TEMPORAL Raster maps for Air dust (PM10) pollution
- SPATIO-TEMPORAL Raster maps of vegetation dust dispersion
- SPATIO-TEMPORAL Raster maps of dust sources

In Situ Measurements: Locations, Timing, and Sampling

In situ measurements were conducted during the dry season at multiple sites in Ilhalainen and Chalkidiki. In Ilhalainen, data collection included nine dust leaf validation sites and three dust traps. In Chalkidiki, a more extensive network was established, comprising 25 dust leaf validation sites and nine dust traps. These measurements resulted in a substantial dataset of samples collected across both regions.

Processing and Integration with EO Data

The *in situ* measurements—including dust trap data, PM10 and PM2.5 monitoring data, as well as mineralogical and elemental analyses—were systematically processed and integrated with Earth Observation (EO) data. The primary purpose of these datasets is to support the validation of quantitative and semi-quantitative models. Specifically, PM10 concentrations and laboratory-derived measurements of dust accumulation on leaves (based on a newly developed method) were used as key validation inputs.

Statistical Analysis

To evaluate the performance and consistency of the models, several statistical measures have been calculated. These include the correlation coefficient (R), the coefficient of determination (R^2), and the root mean square error (RMSE). These metrics provide insights into the agreement between EO-derived products and *in situ* observations, as well as the overall reliability of the modelling approaches.

Additional information

Accuracy Metrics and Validation Approach

In addition to RMSE, several complementary accuracy metrics have been applied to assess model performance. These include the coefficient of determination (R^2) alongside RMSE, both calculated for calibration and validation datasets. For validation, a cross-validation approach was implemented to ensure robust model evaluation and to reduce the risk of overfitting.

Uncertainty Handling and Data Quality

Uncertainties were primarily addressed through rigorous input data quality control procedures. This includes careful screening and preprocessing of both *in situ* and EO datasets to minimize the influence of noise, inconsistencies, and measurement errors. Such measures help to ensure that the derived results are reliable and statistically meaningful.

Reference Data and Spatial Distribution

The reference dataset consists of measurements collected across Chalkidiki and Ithalainen, with spatial distribution aligned to the sampling locations described earlier. Calibration and validation were conducted using geographically corresponding pixels that represent homogeneous areas with sufficient spatial extent relative to the spatial resolution of the remote sensing data. This ensured consistency between field observations and EO-derived information.

Thematic Balance and Model Transferability

To ensure consistency across vegetation types and dust source classes, a physically based (spectral) model was developed using representative tree species commonly found at the study sites. In Chalkidiki, the model was based on *Platanus* species, while in Ithalainen, birch trees were used. The model was then applied to densely vegetated areas, supporting transferability across similar environments.

Spatial and Temporal Alignment

Temporal alignment was achieved by synchronizing *in situ* data collection (ground truth) with drone-based measurements, while satellite data acquisitions closest in time were selected. Spatial alignment relied on matching field sampling locations with corresponding EO pixels, focusing on homogeneous areas suitable for calibration and validation. This ensured both temporal consistency and spatial representativeness in the analysis.

Practical Challenges

Several practical challenges were encountered during the study. These include the influence of traffic-related dust, which may affect measurement accuracy, and limitations in data availability—particularly

the lack of hyperspectral EMIT data for the Ilhalainen site. Additionally, in Chalkidiki, long-range dust transport from Africa introduced further complexity in interpreting the observed dust patterns.

Summary of Accuracy Assessment

Overall Results of the Accuracy Assessment

The comparison between Earth Observation (EO) products and reference data demonstrated that different data sources provide complementary strengths for dust monitoring. Products such as Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) offer spatially and temporally continuous information, which effectively complements high-accuracy but spatially limited *in situ* measurements. When combined with appropriate statistical and machine-learning approaches, these datasets enable more robust, evidence-based air quality assessments and support the analysis of long-term trends.

Key Findings on EO Data Performance

Hyperspectral data, at both leaf and canopy levels, showed a strong capability to detect dust deposition on vegetation. This makes it particularly suitable for mapping the local impacts of dust pollution originating from open-pit mining activities. In contrast, multispectral data from Sentinel-2 have a more limited spectral range, especially in the shortwave infrared (SWIR), which restricts the ability to clearly separate dust effects from other vegetation stress factors. Nevertheless, under controlled environmental assumptions—such as relatively stable soil moisture and the absence of other major pollution sources—Sentinel-2 data can still be effectively used to model dust dispersion. Its key advantages lie in its higher spatial resolution and the availability of long, continuous time series.

Uncertainties and Limitations

Several uncertainties and limitations were identified in the dust monitoring application. These include constraints related to spectral resolution, which affect the differentiation of dust-induced stress from other environmental stressors, as well as variability in environmental conditions such as soil moisture and background pollution. Data availability also plays a role, particularly for hyperspectral datasets, which are not consistently accessible across all study areas.

Reliability for Environmental Assessment

Overall, the produced dust monitoring maps are considered reliable for supporting environmental assessment and decision-making within the MultiMiner project. While individual datasets have inherent limitations, their combined use—integrating EO products, *in situ* measurements, and advanced analytical methods—provides a solid and scientifically robust basis for monitoring dust impacts and informing management strategies.

2.9 Chapter summary

For mineral exploration, the accuracy assessment focused on the comparison of spectral wavelength positions between field spectral measurements and remotely sensed hyperspectral data acquired from UAV, airborne and satellite platforms. Field campaigns in Hochfilzen, Chalkidiki and Kallyntiri provided spectral measurements and laboratory analyzed samples. The assessment emphasized the representativeness of key lithologies, the use of minimally vegetated rock surfaces and the comparison of spectral features across scales.

For vegetation monitoring, the assessment linked *in situ* quadrat measurements with Sentinel-2, PlanetScope, EnMAP and UAV imagery. The measured variables included Leaf Area Index, Fractional Vegetation Cover, Species Richness and derived diversity indicators. The validation relied on regression-based modelling, nested cross-validation, spatial independence checks using Moran's I, and statistical measures such as RMSE, R^2 and MAE. The results support the use of EO products for mapping relative gradients in vegetation status and diversity across the monitored area.

For water quality and acid mine drainage monitoring, EO-derived parameters were compared with *in situ* water quality samples and monitoring data from Chalkidiki and Kirki. Drone-based, PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 data were used together with measurements of parameters such as pH, dissolved iron, heavy metals, turbidity, conductivity, redox, temperature and dissolved oxygen. Partial Least Squares Regression was applied and model performance was evaluated using R^2 and RMSE. The assessment shows the potential of EO data for quantitative and semi-quantitative estimation of selected water quality indicators.

For ground moisture monitoring, SAR-based estimates were evaluated against reference measurements from installed IoT soil moisture sensors and ad-hoc field measurements. Sentinel-1, ALOS-2 PALSAR-2 and multifrequency drone SAR data supported retrieval and modelling activities. Validation included plot-level comparisons, sediment-level and small-area estimates, k-fold cross-validation, and metrics such as R^2 , RMSE, relative RMSE and MAE. The results indicate that SAR-based products can provide consistent information on wetting and drying patterns, particularly for trend monitoring and anomaly detection.

For integrated tailings storage facility monitoring, the assessment combined ground truth sampling, laboratory mineralogical analysis and UAV-based hyperspectral and photogrammetric data. Tailings samples from the Olympias TSF were analyzed using XRD and selected FE-SEM analysis. Spectral interpretation used field spectra, spectral libraries, XRD results and UAV hyperspectral products generated through methods such as Wavelength Mapper, Spectral Angle Mapper and Linear Spectral Unmixing. The assessment was primarily used to verify mineralogical interpretation and to support the integration of mineral composition and surface information into the TSF monitoring workflow.

For dam stability monitoring and open pit stability monitoring, the assessment compared displacement information from EGMS, project-specific Persistent Scatterer processing and GNSS campaign measurements. The comparison focused on line-of-sight displacement trends and selected measurement locations within the tailings dam and open pit. Additional simulated InSAR data were used to support the evaluation of unwrapping error detection. The results confirm the usefulness of InSAR-based measurements for monitoring deformation patterns, while emphasizing the importance of temporal sampling, spatial matching and post-processing of measurement points.

For dust monitoring, *in situ* measurements from Chalkidiki and Ihalainen were integrated with EO data to validate products related to PM10 air dust pollution, vegetation dust dispersion and dust sources.

Reference data included dust trap measurements, PM10 and PM2.5 monitoring data, leaf-based dust measurements, and mineralogical and elemental analyses. The assessment used correlation-based statistics, R^2 , RMSE and cross-validation. Hyperspectral data showed strong potential for detecting dust deposition on vegetation, while multispectral and atmospheric data sources provided complementary information for spatially and temporally continuous dust monitoring.

3 End-user feedback

At the end of the MultiMiner application's development phase, the applications were demonstrated to the participating end-users (companies and users), who were asked to provide feedback. This chapter summarizes the end-user feedback collected after the MultiMiner application demonstrations. The demonstrations were carried out for companies involved in the project and were used to present the thematic applications, show the achieved results, and discuss the practical relevance of the developed Earth Observation (EO)-based approaches. After the demonstrations, the companies received an online feedback survey consisting of ten questions covering learning impact, expectation fulfilment, maturity, relevance, technical credibility, priorities for further development, validation needs, future potential, possible application scenarios, and interest in continued collaboration.

A total of four responses were received from three companies regarding four demonstrations. The survey results therefore provide a structured qualitative view of how the demonstrated applications were perceived by the participating end users. The responses complement the accuracy assessment sections by adding the perspective of practical use, operational relevance, and future uptake. Participants in the survey were assured that the results would be analysed and presented anonymously. For this reason, individual responses will not be discussed here.

3.1 Background and purpose of the feedback survey

The purpose of the feedback survey was to capture how the companies assessed the demonstrated MultiMiner outputs after seeing the application results in a practical demonstration context. The demonstrations served as an interface between the technical work packages and the potential operational users. They allowed the companies to review the project results not only as scientific or technical products, but also with regard to their usability for mine-site monitoring, environmental management, reporting, planning, and decision support.

The survey was structured to cover both immediate reactions to the demonstrations and forward-looking aspects. It asked whether the demonstrations provided new or useful knowledge, whether expectations were met, how mature and credible the applications appeared, which further development steps would increase practical relevance, what additional validation would be needed for operational use, and in which future application scenarios the approaches could be useful.

3.2 Feedback by survey question

Question 1: Learning impact of EO-based applications.

“Have you learned something new / useful about your mine site, thanks to the demonstrated EO-based applications in MultiMiner?”

The first question asked whether the companies had learned something new or useful about their mine site from the demonstrated EO-based applications. Three out of four respondents reported gaining new or useful insights, while one respondent indicated that no additional information was obtained. The reported benefits included improved site-wide visibility, better insights into environmental performance such as revegetation, and enhanced operational oversight, including early detection of possible issues. This shows that the demonstrations were able to communicate the added value of EO-based monitoring for several end users, particularly where the methods extended the spatial overview beyond existing point-based observations.

Question 2: Expectation fulfilment.

“To what extent did this first demonstration meet your expectations regarding the MultiMiner project?”

The second question addressed the extent to which the first demonstration met expectations regarding the MultiMiner project. No respondents reported unmet expectations. The feedback highlighted that the demonstrations provided a clear and practical overview of the project objectives, showed real-world EO applications, and demonstrated the integration of in-situ and remote sensing data. Respondents also noted the value of deriving site-wide information from limited ground measurements, including the role of accuracy validation. Overall, the feedback indicates that the demonstrations were perceived as consistent with the project aims and useful for understanding how the different data sources and methods can be combined.

Question 3: Maturity level of the demonstration.

“How would you assess the current maturity level of the MultiMiner thematic application demonstration?”

The third question asked respondents to assess the current maturity level of the demonstrated thematic application. The feedback presentation notes that two respondents expressed limited confidence in their assessment. This indicates that, while the demonstrations were informative, the maturity of the applications was partly difficult for end users to judge based on a first demonstration alone. The result suggests that maturity perception depends not only on technical results, but also on repeated exposure, clear performance evidence, and the ability to relate the demonstrated outputs to operational workflows.

Question 4: Relevance to organizational challenges.

“How relevant is the demonstrated MultiMiner thematic application approach to challenges in your organization?”

The fourth question focused on the relevance of the demonstrated MultiMiner thematic application approach to challenges in the respondents’ organizations. The feedback identified several areas of relevance, including continuous site monitoring, environmental management, tracking of operational changes, and support for decision-making and planning. This shows that the demonstrated approaches were not perceived only as research outputs, but as potentially useful tools for recurring organizational tasks in mine-site management and environmental monitoring.

Question 5: Technical credibility and robustness.

“How would you rate the technical credibility and robustness of the demonstrated functionality?”

The fifth question asked respondents to rate the technical credibility and robustness of the demonstrated functionality. The overall perception reported in the presentation was one of high technical credibility and reliability. This is important for future uptake, because end users need to trust that EO-based outputs are technically sound, reproducible, and sufficiently robust to support

interpretation and decision-making. The feedback therefore supports the general credibility of the demonstrated methods from the perspective of the participating companies.

Question 6: Priorities for further development.

“What aspects should be prioritized in further development to increase practical relevance?”

The sixth question asked which aspects should be prioritized to increase practical relevance. Respondents identified usability and workflow integration, site-specific customization, improved accuracy and clarity of results, integration with operational and production data, increased automation and update frequency, satellite data availability and validation, and the development of user-friendly tools for end users. This feedback points to a transition from demonstration-level outputs toward operational services, where technical performance must be combined with usability, regular updates, clear interpretation, and integration into existing company workflows.

Question 7: Requirements for operational deployment.

“What additional validation, testing, or evidence would you require before considering operational use?”

The seventh question asked which additional validation, testing, or evidence would be required before considering operational use. Respondents emphasized validation on real mine sites under diverse conditions, demonstration of accuracy, reliability and long-term consistency, comparison with ground-truth or in-situ data, longer-term testing and performance benchmarking, and consideration of user feedback and acceptance. These answers underline the importance of validation and continuous testing as key prerequisites for operational implementation. They also show that end users expect EO-based applications to be evaluated not only technically, but also in relation to their actual operational context.

Question 8: Future potential of the approach.

“Based on the current presentation/demonstration, how would you rate the future potential of the developed thematic application approach?”

The eighth question asked respondents to rate the future potential of the developed thematic application approach based on the current presentation and demonstration. The overall perception was that the approaches have very strong future potential and respond to a clear demand. This indicates that the companies see value in the direction of the MultiMiner developments, especially where EO-based methods can support monitoring tasks that are spatially extensive, repeated over time, or difficult to cover by field measurements alone.

Question 9: Potential application scenarios.

“In which potential application scenarios could you envision the MultiMiner thematic application approach being useful in the future?”

The ninth question asked in which future application scenarios the MultiMiner thematic application approach could be useful. The responses identified operational monitoring as the highest-priority scenario, followed by environmental monitoring such as vegetation, water and disturbance monitoring, progress and performance reporting, audit, transparency and compliance, preparation of reports for authorities, and development of applications for end users such as companies, authorities and consultants. These answers show that the potential use cases extend beyond technical mapping and include communication, reporting, compliance, and stakeholder-oriented applications.

Question 10: Interest in continued collaboration.

“Would you be interested in continued collaboration to further develop and evaluate this approach?”

The tenth question asked whether respondents would be interested in continued collaboration to further develop and evaluate the approach. All respondents expressed interest in continued collaboration. The level of interest ranged from strong and proactive engagement to conditional participation depending on time and resources. Collaboration was seen as valuable for refining and improving the applications, validating them under real operational conditions, and adapting solutions to site-specific needs. This feedback indicates that the demonstrations successfully created a basis for further exchange between the technical project partners and the companies.

4 Conclusion

This chapter presents concluding remarks regarding the accuracy assessment in chapter 2 and a survey of end users described in chapter 3.

Chapter 2 described the accuracy assessment procedures for the MultiMiner application demonstrations. Across the application demonstrations, the accuracy assessment was shaped by the type of product generated. Continuous variables such as vegetation parameters, water quality indicators, ground moisture and dust-related variables were mainly evaluated using regression-oriented metrics. Mineralogical and spectral products relied more strongly on spectral feature comparison, laboratory verification and qualitative interpretation. Deformation monitoring relied on time series comparison and spatially matched displacement measurements.

Reference data played a central role in all assessments. The applications used a broad range of ground reference information, including field spectral measurements, laboratory mineralogical analyses, water samples, vegetation quadrats, soil moisture sensors, GNSS measurements, dust traps and air quality monitoring data. In several applications, stratified or purposefully distributed sampling was used to ensure that relevant surface conditions, material types or environmental gradients were represented.

Spatial and temporal alignment between EO products and reference data was a recurring requirement. The assessments addressed this through synchronized field campaigns, selection of satellite acquisitions close to the field dates, pixel-to-point matching, extraction windows around sample locations, and visual checks in GIS environments. The importance of scale matching was particularly evident where small *in situ* plots or point measurements were compared with coarser satellite pixels.

Uncertainty handling was addressed through data quality control, careful preprocessing, cross-validation, spatial independence checks, residual analysis, and interpretation of practical field constraints. Common sources of uncertainty included sample representativeness, mixed pixels, spatial autocorrelation, sensor noise, co-registration mismatch, atmospheric and illumination conditions, and the heterogeneity of mining environments.

Overall, the accuracy assessment activities demonstrate that the MultiMiner EO products provide useful and complementary information for mineral exploration and mine site monitoring. Their reliability is strongest when products are interpreted in relation to the spatial scale, reference data density, sensor characteristics and validation approach used for each application. Taken together, the assessments support the use of EO-based products for detecting patterns, comparing conditions, monitoring trends and supporting evidence-based interpretation across the different MultiMiner application domains.

To find out how end-users view developments in MultiMiner, a survey was conducted, the results of which are presented in Chapter 3. Across the different application demonstrations, the feedback shows that the MultiMiner approaches were generally perceived as relevant, credible, and promising for practical mine-site applications. A recurring theme is the value of EO data for extending the spatial and temporal view of mine sites beyond what can be achieved with field measurements alone. The ability to combine remote sensing with in-situ data and accuracy validation was repeatedly identified as an important strength, particularly for producing site-wide information from limited ground observations.

The responses also show that practical implementation depends on more than technical feasibility. End users emphasized usability, workflow integration, site-specific adaptation, clear communication of accuracy and uncertainty, reliable data availability, automation, and long-term validation. These aspects are especially relevant if the demonstrated applications are to move from project demonstrations to operational monitoring tools.

The strongest potential application areas identified in the feedback are operational monitoring, environmental monitoring, reporting, compliance, and decision support. These areas align well with the thematic scope of the MultiMiner applications, including vegetation monitoring, water quality and acid mine drainage, ground moisture, tailings storage facility monitoring, stability monitoring, dust monitoring, and mineral exploration. The feedback therefore supports the overall direction of the project: EO-based methods can provide added value where mine-site conditions need to be observed repeatedly, spatially consistently, and in combination with selected in-situ measurements.

Overall, the end-user feedback indicates a positive reception of the demonstrations and a clear interest in further development. The main direction emerging from the responses is to continue improving the applications toward operational readiness by strengthening validation, increasing automation and update frequency, making outputs easier to interpret, and integrating the results into the workflows and decision-making processes of companies and other end users.

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